

accting

AdvanCing behavioural
Change Through
an INclusive Green deal

Consolidated evaluation results report

Organisation Responsible of the Deliverable: K&I

Author(s) name: Gabriele Quinti, Luciano d'Andrea, Marina Cacace

Submission Date: 27 May 2025

<https://accting.eu>

@company/accting

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036504

Project acronym:	ACCTING
Project title:	AdvanCing behavioural Change Through an INclusive Green deal
Grant agreement number:	101036504
Start date of project:	1 February 2022
Duration:	40 months
Deliverable title:	Consolidated Evaluation Results Report
Due date of deliverable:	31 May 2025
Actual date of submission:	27 May 2025
File name:	D6.2_ACCTING_ Consolidated Evaluation
Organisation Responsible for Deliverable:	K&I
Author name(s):	Gabriele Quinti, Luciano d'Andrea, Marina Cacace,
Contributor(s):	Federico Marta, Francesca Pugliese, all partners
Status:	Final
Dissemination Level:	PU ¹
Work Package:	6
Keywords:	impact, evaluation, monitoring, research lines, pilot actions, gender+, vulnerable groups

Please cite as:

Quinti, G., d'Andrea, L., Cacace, M. (2025). *ACCTING D6.2. Consolidated Evaluation Results Report*. Public Deliverable Submitted to the European Commission 27 May 2025. 65 pages.

¹ PU: Public, PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services), RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services), CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).

Revision history

Version	Date	Revised by	Comments
0.1	13 May 2025	Gabriele Quinti, Luciano d'Andrea, Marina Cacace (K&I)	First draft
0.2	19 May 2025	Maria Lucinda Cruz Dos Santos Fonseca, Alina Isabel Pereira Esteves (IGOT)	Quality review
0.3	23 May 2025	Consortium members	General review
0.4	26 May 2025	K&I	Final draft
1.0	27 May 2025	ESF	Final approval prior to submission

Acknowledgement

The ACCTING project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement no. 101036504.

Disclaimer

The information, documentation and figures in this deliverable are written by the ACCTING project consortium under EC grant agreement No. 101036504 and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Table of Contents

Summary.....	10
1. Scope and methodology.....	11
1.1. Scope.....	11
1.2. Methodology.....	12
2. Local knowledge and inclusiveness in disaster risk management.....	15
2.1. Background.....	15
2.2. Description of the cases.....	16
2.3. Recorded impact and key challenges.....	17
2.4. Lessons learned.....	20
3. Care for nature, biodiversity and land use.....	20
3.1. Background.....	20
3.2. Description of the cases.....	21
3.3. Recorded impact and key challenges.....	22
3.4. Lessons learned.....	24
4. Energy and solidarity communities.....	25
4.1. Background.....	25
4.2. Description of the cases.....	25
4.3. Recorded impact and key challenges.....	26
4.4. Lessons learned.....	28
5. Environmental sustainability in micro-businesses led by vulnerable entrepreneurs.....	29
5.1. Background.....	29
5.2. Description of the cases.....	30
5.3. Recorded impact and key challenges.....	31
5.4. Lessons learned.....	33
6. Sustainable food.....	34
6.1. Background.....	34
6.2. Description of the cases.....	35
6.3. Recorded impact and key challenges.....	36
6.4. Lessons learned.....	38
7. Sustainable mobility.....	39
7.1. Background.....	39
7.2. Description of the cases.....	40
7.3. Recorded impact and key challenges.....	41
7.4. Lessons learned.....	43
8. Volunteering.....	44
8.1. Background.....	44
8.2. Description of the cases.....	45
8.3. Recorded impact and key challenges.....	45
8.4. Lessons learned.....	46
9. A cross-cutting analysis of the initiatives.....	48
9.1. A comparative view of the impacts.....	48
9.2. Direct impact: evidence of appreciable change.....	49
9.3. Indirect impact: mixed evidence of precursors to longer-term change.....	49

9.4. Cross-cutting impact: the challenge of sustainability and replicability/scalability ...	50
10. Conclusions	51
10.1. Cultural shifts: beyond environmental awareness.....	51
10.2. Agency: the social dimension of change and resistance	51
10.3. Strategic action: engaging with social-environmental tensions	52
10.4. Resources and relations: pooling and coordinating efforts.....	53
11. Limitations.....	54
References.....	55
ANNEX: Synthetic view of the recorded impacts	57

List of tables

Table 1: Research Lines and Pilot Actions within ACCTING.....	11
Table 2: Short description of impact areas.....	13
Table 3: The cases considered in PA1 and RL1.....	16
Table 4: The cases considered in PA2 and RL2.....	21
Table 5: The cases considered in PA3 and RL3.....	25
Table 6: Vulnerability factors to which micro-entrepreneurs were exposed.....	30
Table 7: Economic sector of the micro enterprises.....	30
Table 8: The cases considered in PA5, PA6, RL5 and RL6.....	35
Table 9: The cases considered in PA7, PA8, and RL7.....	40
Table 10: Synthetic view of the impacts identified in all intervention sectors.....	48

List of acronyms

CEE	Central and Eastern Europe
DM/DRM	Disaster Risk Management
EEN	Energy Efficiency Networks
ESC	Energy and Solidarity Community
FD	Sustainable Food
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
ME	Disadvantaged Micro-Entrepreneurs
MO	Sustainable Mobility
NB	Care For Nature, Biodiversity and Land Use
NE	Northern Europe
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PA	Pilot Action
RL	Research Line
SE	Southern Europe
SME	Small- and Medium-sized Enterprise
WE	Western Europe

The ACCTING Project

It is acknowledged by now that the global climate crisis is not only an ecological crisis but also an economic, social and political crisis, with devastating effects on individuals and societies. These negative effects are not evenly distributed within societies. It is the poorer, marginalised and vulnerable groups who are the most acutely affected, exacerbating existing socio-economic inequalities.

The European Green Deal foresees the efficient use of resources for a circular and clean economy. However, inequalities emerge in the context of its policy and interventions.

The EU-funded ACCTING project takes these considerations as a starting point for a complex series of research and experimental activities aimed at identifying, analysing and testing policies and initiatives capable of responding to this crisis, mitigating its effects on the most vulnerable and helping them play a significant role in the pursuit of greater environmental sustainability.

The project mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal, focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies and supporting behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

The project explores the impact of Green Deal policy initiatives on individual and collective behaviours, provides evidence, and empowers policymakers and stakeholders to anticipate policy responses and potential negative influences, and mitigate such impacts in decision-making. ACCTING collects new data on Green Deal policy interventions and co-designs and implements pilot actions to reduce or prevent policy-related inequalities and advance behavioural change for an inclusive and equal European Green Deal.

Project Consortium

	European Science Foundation (ESF)
	Örebro University (ORU)
	Yellow Window (YW)
	Knowledge and Innovation (K&I)
	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation (ZSI)
	Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)
	ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability, European Secretariat
	Sabancı University (SU)
	Instituto de Geografia e Ordenamento de Território (IGOT)
	South-East European Research Center (SEERC)
	Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi (UAIC)
	European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)
	University of Gothenburg (UGOT)

Summary

This report consolidates the impact evaluation findings from a wide range of social innovation activities examined through ACCTING's eight Research Lines (RLs) and ten Pilot Actions (PAs), organised around key thematic areas connected to the European Green Deal. The aim was to test the ACCTING theoretical framework, translated into a broad impact evaluation approach, and to identify which areas of impact are more readily achievable by social innovation initiatives, and which require further development and a better understanding of the support needed.

The report is structured into thematic sections, each focusing on a different area: disaster risk management, biodiversity and land use, energy and solidarity communities, environmental sustainability in micro-enterprises, sustainable food, sustainable mobility, and volunteering. Each section includes a background overview, descriptions of the selected cases, an analysis of recorded impacts, a discussion of key challenges, and a summary of lessons learned. The final section presents an analysis crossing the thematic areas and identifying common trends, enabling factors, and barriers to inclusive environmental change. The evaluation is guided by a comprehensive framework covering nine impact areas, organised in three main categories (direct impacts, indirect impacts/precursors of change, cross-cutting impacts).

The findings show that participatory and community-based initiatives can generate positive environmental and social outcomes, especially when vulnerable groups are recognised as active agents and their knowledge and expertise are incorporated into the design and development process of the initiatives. Improvements in awareness, inclusion, and social cohesion were common across cases. Nonetheless, several challenges in generating significant impacts through the initiatives still persist, such as limited institutional support, the marginal presence of gender+/intersectional approaches, and weak mechanisms for policy scalability.

The Conclusion section synthesises key insights from the initiatives analysed, grouped under four overarching themes (Culture, Agency, Strategic action, Resources and relations). First, the conclusions stress that cultural change must go beyond environmental awareness, tackling entrenched beliefs that hinder inclusive sustainability in a broad range of related domains. Second, the conclusions highlight the importance of the social dimension of change, acknowledging both supportive and resisting agency, especially from vulnerable communities. Third, they identify strategic factors that promote deep and lasting change, including engaging with social-environmental tensions, diversification and flexible adaptation to context. Lastly, the conclusions address the fragility of grassroots efforts, noting that sustainability, replicability and scalability often falter due to limited resources and support. Broader alliances and cross-sector partnerships are essential to reinforce these initiatives, while also allowing for holistic responses to the needs of intersectional vulnerable groups.

Finally, a brief section outlines the main limitations of the impact evaluation, which stem from the diversity of the analysed initiatives, differing methodological approaches, time constraints, and potential self-reporting bias. These factors affected both the comparability of cases and the generalisability of the findings.

1. Scope and methodology

1.1. Scope

This report presents synthetic results of the impact evaluation of all experimental activities carried out under ACCTING, that is, all research and innovation activities promoting a just environmental transition that were studied or supported by the project. It therefore covers two main groups of activities: the Research Lines and the Pilot Actions.

Research Lines (RLs) are interdisciplinary, multi-partner thematic studies, each linked to a Green Deal policy area. RLs follow a case study methodology, looking at different types of initiatives that support inclusive behavioural change towards environmentally friendly social practices.

- Research Lines results are synthesised in dedicated RL-level reports (White et al. 2025; Gajdusek et al. 2025; Boostani et al. 2025; Quinti et al. 2025; Moreno et al. 2025; Balkmar et al. 2025; Pugliese et al. 2025) and the overall D3.3 report (Zorell et al. 2025).

Pilot actions (PAs) are the result of the “Creativity step” of the project which, through the methodology of the Open Studios (Boyer et al. 2011; Kerremans et al. 2023; Denis & Strid 2024; Strid & Denis 2024), capitalised on the results of the first research cycle to develop action ideas with a high innovation potential to be tested within the timeframe of the project through the involvement – as promoters – of external stakeholders.

- Pilot Actions results are synthesised in D5.7

In both cases, impact evaluation within ACCTING aims to generate new knowledge about the **conditions for inclusive behavioural change associated with Green Deal policies**, based on experimental studies (RLs) and real-life tests (PAs).

The list of RLs and PAs is given below.

Table 1: Research Lines and Pilot Actions within ACCTING

RL no.	RL title	PA no.	PA title
RL1	Valorising local knowledge in the frame of community-based disaster management and mitigating exposure	PA1	Next Time, better and more inclusive
RL2	Biodiversity and land use restrictions	PA2	Wild eyes: biodiversity crisis knowledge
RL3	Energy communities, energy poverty and community energy schemes	PA3	Awards for inclusive energy communities
RL4	Intensifying the adoption of energy-efficiency and other pro-environmental measures in micro/small enterprises	PA4	Hands-on small-scale support for vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs

RL no.	RL title	PA no.	PA title
RL5	Improving food security and healthy diets in vulnerable communities	PA5	Garden B&B
RL6	Values associated with Environmentally Sustainable Food Consumption/ESFC	PA6	F.E.T. (Food Everywhere Toolkit)
RL7	Transport poverty and sustainable travel: families in socially vulnerable areas	PA7	Green to school: sustainable commutes
RL8	Post-lockdown sustainable mobilities: centring cycling and walking	PA8	Wheels for justice
		PA9	Kick-starting volunteering
		PA10	Cultivating change-makers: youth empowerment through activism

A total of 99 cases were analysed (from both RLs and PAs), 75 of which are initiatives and 24 are individuals (micro-entrepreneurs from RL4 and PA4; see Section 5). It was decided not to include in the impact analysis the six cases studied in RL8 (dealing with mobility policies promoted by city authorities), as the focus of the study was not the cases as such, but the citizens' reaction to them. For this reason, any possible comparison with the other cases, and particularly those promoting cycling, would inevitably have been misleading.

To ensure the anonymity of participants and promoters, all initiatives are coded and presented with reference to the European region rather than the country in which they were implemented². To facilitate the reading of the text, the following acronym will be used for identifying the European Regions: Central and Eastern Europe – CEE; Northern Europe – NE; Southern Europe – SE; Western Europe – WE

1.2. Methodology

The evaluation impact analysis was carried out based on an approach that was presented in D6.1 “Impact Evaluation Framework”, delivered on 31 October 2023. It includes ten impact areas (see Table 2) which can be divided into those that indicate **direct impacts** (linked to inclusive behavioural change), those that indicate **indirect impacts** (representing precursors of change, relevant here as areas of potential impact), and those that represent **cross-cutting impacts**, which can be applied to both direct and indirect impact areas.

² *Central and Eastern Europe*: Albania, Bosnia, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Kosovo, Latvia, Lithuania, Montenegro, Northern Macedonia, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Turkey. *Northern Europe*: Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden. *Southern Europe*: Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Spain, Portugal. *Western Europe*: Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Switzerland. There were no cases in the British Isles (United Kingdom and Ireland).

A detailed analysis of the impact areas is provided in D6.1. A short description is given below.

Table 2: Short description of impact areas

Direct impact areas		
1.	Individual and collective pro-environmental behavioural change	Impact in terms of change both at the individual level (e.g., changes in dietary habits, mobility patterns) and at the collective level (e.g., promoting energy communities with an inclusive perspective, involving citizens in disaster mitigation strategies).
2.	Reduction of territorial vulnerabilities and improved sustainability	Impact in terms of reduced vulnerability of the affected territory, including, e.g., low income, poor housing, underemployment and unemployment, exposure to criminality/lack of security or lack of or poor access to adequate public/social services.
3.	Reduction of gender+/intersectional inequalities	Impact as potentially positive distributional effects of the different initiatives or policy measures on inequalities (based on, e.g., age, disability, gender identity, migration status, ethnicity/race, or sexual orientation) in an intersectional perspective.
Indirect / Potential impact areas (impact precursors)		
4.	Agreement and satisfaction of participants	The agreement and satisfaction levels towards environmentally sustainable choices, practices and policies.
5.	Acknowledgement of vulnerable groups as key actors in environmental transitions	The involvement of vulnerable groups as leaders or key actors in the design and implementation of initiatives or policy measures.
6.	Inclusion of local/traditional knowledge	The existence and effectiveness of practices where local or traditional knowledge is significantly involved and integrated in the design and implementation of actions, allowing for inclusive problem identification and management.
7.	Comprehensiveness ³	The range of factors and dimensions that are considered in the initiatives and their consequent ability to trigger behavioural change and limit unintended consequences.
Crosscutting impact areas		
8.	Sustainability	The ability of an initiative to continue to have an effect over time, ideally taking on an irreversible character.

³ The area, 'Comprehensiveness of the focus of the actions analysed', revealed difficult to apply in a sufficiently homogeneous way across RLs and PAs and is therefore not included in this analysis.

9.	Replicability and scalability	The ability of an initiative to be replicable elsewhere or reproduced on a larger geographical or institutional scale, going beyond the original socio-cultural and institutional context.
10.	Unexpected or additional impact	Both unanticipated and unintended impacts (including the undesirable side effects of an intervention)

The identification of these as relevant impact areas for ACCTING suggests the project's **Theory of Change**, which posits that the adoption of specific approaches (e.g., intersectionality, trans-epistemic practices, vulnerable groups identified as key actors) increases the chances that inclusive environmental change will occur and be sustainable over time, by virtue of being grounded, responsive, legitimate and with a strong focus on the social and collective dimensions of change.

This is synthetically represented in the figure below, where the elements of the impact evaluation framework are organised according to the **logic and flow** of the evaluation process.

Evaluation logic and flow

The **sources of information** have differed for the Research Lines (RLs) and Pilot Actions (PAs). For the RLs, the main sources have been the final research reports included in Deliverable 3.3 (Report on second-cycle experimental studies), supplemented by country-level reports produced by national researchers. For the PAs, the primary sources have been the final reports submitted by the promoters, which included a dedicated section structured around the impact evaluation areas outlined earlier (see Table 2). Additional sources include Deliverables 5.6 (Pilot Actions monitoring report) and 5.7 (Pilot Actions implementation report), which provide information gathered through the monitoring activities of the Pilot Actions, carried out in accordance with the principles of Developmental Evaluation (Patton 1994, 2006), integrated by Participatory Evaluation (Cousins & Whitmore 1998; Fetterman & Wandersman 2004). Insights from the Qualitative Comparative Analysis conducted as part of the RL

research (D3.4 Overall Report on the Results of the Eight Thematic Research Lines: Intersectional and Qualitative Comparative Analyses)⁴ have also been taken into account.

By reviewing all available documents, each initiative was analysed for its impacts, which were then categorised according to the areas outlined in Table 2. **Summary tables by thematic area** were subsequently created (see Table 1), presenting the recorded impacts.

Once the tables were compiled, they were reviewed iteratively by the researchers in the K&I team to ensure consistency. They were then submitted to the other consortium partners involved and further refined following their review.

These tables are included in the **Annex** ('Synthetic view of the recorded impact') for reference. They form the basis for the summary assessment presented in Table 10, as well as for the comments and insights discussed throughout the report.

Following this section on the scope and methodology of the evaluation exercise, the impact assessment analysis is presented separately for each thematic area: Disaster risk management (section two), Biodiversity (section three), Energy and solidarity communities (section four), Environmental sustainability in disadvantaged micro-enterprises (section five), Sustainable food (section six), Sustainable mobility (section seven) and Volunteering (section eight).

Each thematic section follows a consistent structure, comprising a brief background, a description of the analysed cases, a summary of the impacts, an analysis of main trends and critical issues, and reflections on lessons learned.

The subsequent sections offer a cross-cutting analysis, synthesising the main insights that emerged (section nine), followed by a brief set of conclusions (section ten). Finally, the methodological constraints and limitations of the report are outlined (section eleven).

2. Local knowledge and inclusiveness in disaster risk management

2.1. Background

Local communities often play an active role in preventing, preparing for, and responding to natural hazards related to climate change. However, civil protection authorities frequently adopt a predominantly top-down approach, with limited genuine involvement of local communities and citizens in knowledge production, decision-making, and local planning. In this context, it is crucial to recognise that local communities are not merely passive recipients of aid or instructions, but active participants in natural disaster preparedness, prevention, and management. There is therefore a need to learn from their knowledge and expertise, and to empower them to enhance their resilience.

Disaster management – both in the preparedness and emergency phases – is primarily led by authorities that may include public actors such as civil protection at various levels, fire brigades, law enforcement agencies, local authorities, social and health institutions, and relevant scientific bodies, as well as other actors such as NGOs, volunteers, and private

companies. Some authorities are currently working to broaden their approach by directly involving local communities in Disaster Risk Management (DRM), recognising them as holders of essential and valuable local knowledge. These efforts are sometimes complemented by an attempt to address different forms of vulnerability and inequality through an intersectional gender+ perspective.

This section examines the cases presented in RL1 (analysing local knowledge uptake in the frame of disaster management) and PA1 (aimed at empowering communities for disaster resilience).

2.2. Description of the cases

Overall, 11 cases are considered. A short description is given in the table below.

Table 3: The cases considered in PA1 and RL1

Code	Location	Description
DM1	SE	An initiative aimed at empowering local communities to increase their wildfire resilience.
DM2	SE	An urban municipality in a metropolitan area that was hit by severe flooding in November 2023.
DM3	SE	A medium-sized city that experienced two flash floods in May 2023.
DM4	SE	A small, mountainous municipality that was hit by an intense storm that caused flooding and landslides in September 2022.
DM5	SE	A densely populated municipality on the outskirts of a big city that is exposed to flash floods and heat waves.
DM6	SE	A village that is frequently exposed to natural hazards such as flash floods and occasional landslides.
DM7	NE	An initiative aimed at improving crisis preparedness by supporting local networks.
DM8	NE	A sparsely populated municipality that was severely affected by forest fires in the summer of 2018.
DM9	CEE	A small forest village that faced wide wildfires in 2021.
DM10	CEE	A collaborative project aimed at improving local engagement and fire resilience in forest villages.
DM11	CEE	A unit established by the municipality of a big city to improve forest fire intervention in rural areas through collaboration with forest villages.

2.3. Recorded impact and key challenges

2.3.1. Gains in awareness, gaps in engagement

The first noticeable impact of citizen-involving actions in DRM is an increase in public awareness of disasters. This is often achieved through awareness-raising and risk reduction education programmes, which are generally top-down in nature (e.g., a programme promoted by a civil protection authority in SE or an initiative in NE). While these initiatives may reach a large number of citizens, participants are typically passive recipients of information rather than active contributors.

To improve inclusivity, face-to-face events and workshops are also organised to enable participation by those without reliable internet access or prior experience with community-led initiatives. In many cases, such efforts have led to increased preparedness for risks (e.g., floods, wildfires) at both individual and community levels. For instance, in DM1, people reported feeling “more educated on issues related to forest fire management and therefore a little safer”.

This enhanced awareness has, in some cases, contributed to behavioural changes in how individuals and communities deal with hazards – ideally including the adoption of safer routines. However, the number of people deeply engaged in these activities remains relatively limited, partly due to the lack of secured funding to support ongoing training and engagement efforts.

2.3.2. Institutional learning on vulnerabilities and persistent blind spots

Another notable impact is the growing awareness among authorities of the complexity of social vulnerability. Most authorities demonstrate a solid understanding of how social vulnerability intersects with disaster risk management (DRM). This awareness influences disaster preparedness efforts, such as vulnerability mapping and targeted messaging for specific vulnerable groups (which has become standard practice e.g., in DM3) and informs both the methods and priorities used in emergency response.

However, in some cases (e.g., in DM2), the focus is limited to the more practical aspects of vulnerability – such as mobility, communication, and access to food. In these instances, commonly identified vulnerable groups include the elderly, children, persons with disabilities, migrants, autistic individuals, and people with celiac disease. Meanwhile, other important vulnerability dimensions, such as gender, gender identity, and socio-economic status, tend to be overlooked.

2.3.3. Blending knowledge systems - but only in rural DRM

The cases studied highlight the recognition of local communities, particularly certain groups such as the elderly, as holders of valuable local knowledge for the prevention and management of natural hazards. However, this recognition appears to occur only in rural areas.

In DM1, for example, various mechanisms (e.g., meetings, templates) have been developed to integrate community-generated data, such as mapped water sources or vulnerability assessments, into the data used by civil protection authorities. This has helped demonstrate the practical value of local knowledge, including historical data on past events, in preventing and managing forest fires.

In DM10, civil protection authorities, working with academics and NGOs, introduced procedures to incorporate the knowledge of vulnerable groups and to integrate different types of knowledge. For example, traditional knowledge of forest use was complemented with technical information.

In DM3, the civil protection system reinforced a community network to enable two-way communication for managing emergencies and recovery. This also included the use of everyday local practices, such as techniques for clearing obstructions from watercourses. Similar patterns were observed in other rural contexts (e.g., DM4, DM8, and DM9).

The use of local knowledge in rural contexts has often led to a greater appreciation of biodiversity and natural resources as assets to be protected, both to preserve ecosystems and to prevent future disasters (e.g., those resulting from increased deforestation). This approach involves the development or strengthening of trans-epistemic practices, which blend local, technical, and scientific knowledge, particularly in disaster prevention, but also more broadly across DRM.

Conversely, in urban areas, the integration of local knowledge into DRM practices is often limited. This is primarily due to the complexity of urban environments, where the diverse and transient nature of communities can hinder the accumulation and application of localised experiential knowledge. Additionally, urban DRM strategies frequently prioritise technical and centralised approaches, which may overlook the value of community-based insights. In some cases, authorities explicitly stated that there was no local expertise deemed useful for DRM. An exception can be represented by DM3, in a medium-sized city, where citizen committees were involved in the revision of the Civil Protection Plan.

2.3.4. Weak integration of gender+ perspectives in DRM practices

Recognition of the gender perspective remains weak. Professions and organisations involved in disaster risk management (DRM) are still predominantly male-dominated working environments, with limited sensitivity to gender issues. Efforts to address vulnerability from an intersectional perspective are minimal, and few professionals within DRM agencies acknowledge the gendered nature of disasters and inequalities.

Concrete examples are rare. In one case in CEE, the initiative of a female sociologist enabled better access to village women's knowledge and its more effective integration into the project. In DM11, a female firefighter advocated for the inclusion of women in fire management. In another instance in SE, meetings were held to involve women, despite constraints in time and resources, in initiatives aimed at preventing and managing wildfires.

On a more positive note, women's representation in leadership positions is increasingly reported, both within official authorities (e.g., in one case in SE) and at the community level (e.g., DM8). Women leaders are also viewed as role models, as seen in DM3 and DM9. This shift is an important driver of change, contributing, such as in two cases in NE, to modified approaches to preparedness, including greater attention to women and a stronger emphasis on collective action.

2.3.5. Ambivalent and contradictory attitudes to citizen involvement

In the cases examined, the impact on DRM governance has remained limited.

Within DRM systems, communities and citizens, especially those who are disadvantaged, continue to be largely excluded from decision-making processes, or, at best, play only a

subordinate role. While some authorities have introduced mechanisms to facilitate the involvement of communities and vulnerable groups, these efforts are typically temporary and project-based (e.g., DM7), and often only the most active local actors are considered (e.g., in DM8). In most instances, community self-organisation and self-learning in response to disasters have had no meaningful influence on DRM governance. A partial exception is DM1, where coordination committees were established in each village. This initiative resulted in the development of a wildfire prevention plan and the implementation of effective first response mechanisms, both centred on active citizen participation.

The reception of volunteers in emergency response varies considerably. On one hand, they are valued for the support they offer. On the other hand, they are sometimes seen as complicating disaster management efforts and, in some cases, are even dismissed or belittled by DRM authorities (as reported in DM2). Uncertainty about the availability and competence of volunteers, coupled with the command-and-control nature of response systems, may hinder the participation of these helpers.

Overall, the attitude of authorities towards the involvement of diverse actors in DRM governance is contradictory. While they formally express support for community-led initiatives and the participation of local stakeholders, decision-making processes remain largely unchanged. There are, however, a few isolated efforts to promote more inclusive approaches, which, even if indirectly, help enhance the legitimacy of citizens in playing an active role in DRM. In DM11 (CE), a local firefighter unit initiated engagement with citizens to involve them in fire prevention and intervention mechanisms. Over time, this initiative has evolved into a complex and sustained interaction

2.3.6. Instances of distrust by communities and citizens

Where people are meaningfully involved, they tend to respond positively. However, instances of public distrust have also been reported. In DM1, although engaging with villagers was a fundamental aspect of the project from the onset, some community members who were initially interested in participating withdrew once it became clear that the initiative would not include the construction of new infrastructure for wildfire prevention. Similarly, in DM2, mistrust emerged due to delays in the development or improvement of flood protection infrastructure, when the implementation of infrastructure did not accelerate significantly following a promising dialogue between the villagers, who were organised into committees, and the DRM authorities.

Despite this, in the DM1 area, stakeholders have expressed a continued willingness to collaborate, aiming to better integrate bottom-up approaches into institutional civil protection procedures. In contrast, conflicts persist in DM2. Tensions have also been reported in DM4 and DM6.

2.3.7. Sustainable actions, but rarely replicable

The innovative actions analysed involve a range of stakeholders, including public authorities, universities, and NGOs. This collaboration ensures their sustainability over time and supports the continuation of the change processes they initiate. However, in some cases, these actions are embedded in projects (e.g., DM1, DM7, DM10) that are designed to conclude after a set period, meaning their sustainability is not guaranteed.

Many of the most successful examples developed in spite of, rather than because of, the DRM authorities, which limits their replicability. More critically, these initiatives are highly context-specific, making them challenging to adapt to other settings. That said, some exceptions do

exist. A notable example is the worksheets developed in DM1, which include information on residents, community mapping, prevention and preparedness measures, and guidelines for response and recovery. These materials can be adapted to various local or regional contexts, and they have been translated into English to make them more easily replicable. The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) has expressed interest in incorporating them into its guidance materials.

2.4. Lessons learned

2.4.1. Challenging the current culture of disaster risk management

DRM authorities tend to replicate top-down operational models designed to maintain full control. The main argument against participatory and inclusive approaches that incorporate local knowledge is that they add complexity, introduce potentially unreliable inputs, and make the process more time-consuming and uncertain. As a result, such approaches are often perceived by DRM authorities as disruptive elements to be avoided or tightly managed.

This change in perspective towards bottom-up approaches requires corresponding changes in procedures and practices, some of which are already tested and available. A good example, mentioned above, can be found in DM1 (co-designed wildfire prevention plan). The key question, however, is how to incorporate these practices into the operational protocols and professional toolkits of DRM operators. It is important to stress that such change should encompass the wide range of actors involved in the civil protection system (e.g., firefighters, police, forest guards, Red Cross and equivalent organisations).

2.4.2. Identifying and supporting the change agents

Despite the overall unfavourable situation outlined above, the analysis also highlights the presence of participatory and inclusive practices. Authorities frequently engage various actors, including voluntary organisations that incorporate DRM into their mission, as well as members and bodies representing the scientific community.

Furthermore, there are professionals and practitioners working within or alongside DRM authorities who are advocating for more open models and can be seen as 'change agents', gradually transforming the way government operates in DRM. These individuals can be found across a wide range of sectors: in civil protection, within structured NGOs, in fire and police services, in academia, and within social/health services. They include technicians, social experts, civil servants, and volunteers. While their numbers may be small, they are already influencing DRM policies and practices.

It is essential to identify, connect, amplify, and support these individuals as much as possible to ensure their impact continues to grow.

3. Care for nature, biodiversity and land use

3.1. Background

The interaction between humans and nature is becoming increasingly central to public awareness, particularly in the context of global warming, which scientific reports highlight as having a significant and alarming impact at every level. This marks an unprecedented shift in recent decades. Within this framework, changes in biodiversity have become more physically

apparent to citizens and more visible in daily life compared to the more abstract concept of climate change. In this perspective, protected areas have been established and are becoming more widespread. According to the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), a protected area is defined as “a clearly defined geographical area that is recognised, dedicated, and managed through legal or other effective means to achieve the long-term conservation of nature, ecosystem services, and associated cultural values”. These areas are places where active citizens unite, sharing a common commitment to caring for nature.

This section seeks to examine the impacts of actions related to the connection between active citizens and biodiversity that underpin two ACCTING activities.

The analysis is based on cases drawn from RL2 (exploring the alignment between biodiversity land-use restrictions and the socio-economic needs of vulnerable groups), and PA2 (participatory biodiversity conservation project).

3.2. Description of the cases

This section considers 12 cases, all of which relate to rural contexts (with only one example of an urban pro-nature initiative included). These cases primarily involve areas closely connected to local neighbourhoods. In each case, citizens, whether as observers or active participants, are engaged in a range of activities led by both formal and more informal groups. A brief description of the cases is provided in the table below.

Table 4: The cases considered in PA2 and RL2.

Code	Location	Description
NB1	CEE	An active pro-nature initiative in a village located close to an UNESCO-protected natural area, facing environmental challenges due to plans to activate a limestone quarry.
NB2	CEE	Pro-nature and environmental activities addressing administrative shortcomings in ecological protection, particularly concerning a glass wool production facility exploiting nearby resources.
NB3	SE	An organisation supporting citizen science engagement and awareness campaigns on biodiversity change and preparing fact-based solutions.
NB4	CEE	Awareness-raising activities on climate change mitigation and small-scale ecological actions in a water catchment area characterised by floodplain rehabilitation.
NB5	CEE	Initiative for floodplain rehabilitation, local organic farming and community education on sustainable practices in a water catchment area exposed to floods.
NB6	CEE	Initiative for floodplain restoration, reintroduction of native species, and energy independence for the municipality in a village within marginalised sub-regions.
NB7	SE	Initiative focused on environmental awareness, empowered community action, fostered sustainable consumption and intergenerational knowledge exchange in the frame of an agroforestry project.
NB8	SE	Initiative engaging citizens in biodiversity conservation through active

Code	Location	Description
		participation in environmental monitoring in the frame of a volunteer programme.
NB9	CEE	Residents and activists involved in actions against landfill development with European funding.
NB10	CEE	Actions aimed at protecting biodiversity and restoring balance in deforested areas, with community members active in reforestation and wildlife monitoring.
NB11	CEE	Initiatives aimed at defending nomads' grazing rights against state policies restricting movement.
NB12	CEE	Actions aimed at stopping coal mine operations encroaching on forests and villages, resisting state-supported destruction.

3.3. Recorded impact and key challenges

3.3.1. Overall positive impact of community initiatives

Almost all the initiatives resulted in positive changes in the management of natural resources at the local level, although the degree of success varied. In NB9, residents and activists engaged in actions opposing the development of a landfill funded by the European Union, reclaiming control over their livelihoods and the already constructed site, which is now expected to remain unused. These efforts ultimately led to a temporary halt to environmentally harmful interventions.

In NB5, the initiative contributed to the restoration of a floodplain to mitigate flash floods. Similarly, in NB6, floodplain restoration was undertaken alongside the reintroduction of native species to improve the area's ecological condition. In NB3, the project supported the protection of local transhumance routes as a means of preserving and enhancing biodiversity.

As previously mentioned, levels of success varied. For example, in the case of NB12, where the goal was to halt coal mining in a local forest, the objective was not achieved despite strong social mobilisation.

From comparative analysis, the following factors emerged as characterising the most successful experiences: a prevalent pro-environmental attitude among the local authority/ies; long-established channels for participation; active participation of women; and the prior activist experience of the citizen groups involved.

3.3.2. Boosting active citizenship

Regardless of their level of success, the actions generally led to a widespread increase in active citizenship, the formation of community alliances and networks, and a rise in public enthusiasm. In some cases, the scope of activism expanded to include additional or broader environmental issues.

In NB4, for instance, there was a growing recognition of the importance of civic engagement and greater awareness of the role played by the nature service in flood protection. In NB8, community involvement extended to encompass wider nature conservation efforts. In certain

cases (e.g., NB5), these developments also contributed to the emergence of a new generation of community leaders.

3.3.3. Community-driven environmental awareness

The initiatives have undoubtedly played a significant role in raising environmental awareness, achieved through a variety of approaches. In NB5, considerable efforts were made to transfer knowledge about environmental values and to educate the community on sustainable practices. In NB12, schools were actively involved in specific activities, helping to disseminate key messages more broadly through students and their families.

NB8 placed emphasis on sustainable tourism and heritage conservation, presenting these as vital assets for the region's future. In NB9, educational activities were implemented to counteract illegal practices that cause environmental harm.

3.3.4. Fostering community cohesion through environmental initiatives

One of the main impacts of the initiatives has been an increase in social cohesion within the communities involved. In NB7, the pro-nature action was closely tied to the social fabric, resulting in a lasting partnership that strengthened community bonds. In NB2, growing cohesion within the community was observed, notably including the active involvement of the Roma population.

In NB1, the collective opposition to quarry development, which mobilised the entire village, intensified social interaction and fostered solidarity, leading to what was described as an “intergenerational negotiation of new values”.

Finally, in NB3, the initiative facilitated new relationships and collaborations that extended beyond the original aims of the pilot action, engaging researchers, local cultural associations, and sustainable tourism projects. This helped to build stronger community cohesion and a shared vision for the region's future.

3.3.5. Women's leadership in environmental action

The empowerment of women emerged as a significant outcome in several cases in NB 10, 11 and 12. Both initiatives in this context involved vulnerable groups in leadership roles, with a strong emphasis on the participation of women. In NB11, “a strong female leadership formed a new role model to keep the nomadic lifestyle and its traditional environment alive”. In NB12, female leaders adopted an explicitly gender-conscious approach in their opposition to coal mining operations, embracing an open and dialogical stance that included non-traditional perspectives, such as those of LGBTQI+ movements.

Gender roles were also addressed in an initiative in Central and Eastern Europe (NB10), which sought to protect biodiversity based on the understanding that “developing a better shared vision of a liveable future with a view to the next generation affects gender roles”. In Southern Europe, NB3 tackled the empowerment of women in transhumance communities, offering training on biodiversity as part of the effort. In NB7, activities were carried out with migrant women to foster a sense of solidarity within a self-organised group.

Other initiatives, such as NB1, NB2, NB4, and NB6 in Central and Eastern Europe, and NB8 in Southern Europe, also incorporated a gender perspective, including women in leadership roles. However, these efforts did not result in measurable changes in status, reduced

inequality, or shifts in traditional gender roles. As noted in a report by a local research team involved in ACCTING, “gender approaches to traditional gender roles remain neglected”.

3.4. Lessons learned

3.4.1. Agency for change and resistance of marginalised communities

The initiatives reviewed span a wide range of sectors, from flood protection, coal-mining opposition, to transhumance management, yet all demonstrate meaningful citizen participation in environmental protection. Notably, marginalised groups such as migrants and pastoralists often play a proactive, and even leading, role. In other instances, however, marginalised communities have actively or passively resisted broader climate policies, for example by opposing reforestation projects or decarbonisation measures that would threaten their livelihoods.

Recognising and analysing the roots of such resistance is essential, particularly when it involves vulnerable populations. By understanding their concerns, we can deploy effective tools to manage conflict, foster constructive dialogue, and harness local networks, resources and knowledge. In doing so, we not only address points of contention but also strengthen these communities’ roles as agents of change. Establishing stable channels for negotiation and adopting adaptive management practices would allow policies to evolve dynamically in response to bottom-up input.

3.4.2. Integrating social and environmental goals for stronger communities

Many of the initiatives examined in this section pursue both social objectives, such as enhancing community cohesion, integrating marginalised groups and creating employment opportunities, and environmental sustainability goals. In numerous grassroots projects, social and environmental aims do not merely coexist but actively reinforce one another.

These examples underscore the importance of aligning social and environmental policies to bolster community-based efforts and mitigate resistance. Including in negotiation processes with policy-makers groups that are active/aware on environmental issues but also voice concerns related to, for example, community livelihoods or culture, can be particularly valuable in this regard.

3.4.3. Longer-term impact of citizen-led initiatives

While some initiatives – such as NB12’s attempt to halt coal mining – were only partially successful or failed to meet their immediate objectives, they nonetheless sparked powerful processes of citizen mobilisation. These movements have laid crucial groundwork for future efforts to address other environmental and social challenges. They have contributed to the emergence of a new generation of community leaders who can help steer communities towards more active citizenship by identifying locally meaningful material and immaterial gains that support sustained bottom-up mobilisation and engagement.

Accordingly, evaluations should extend beyond short-term outcomes to consider the longer-term social dynamics that these initiatives set in motion. Understanding how citizen engagement is activated and sustained can reveal deeper measures of success and guide the design of more resilient, community-driven projects.

4. Energy and solidarity communities

4.1. Background

A Renewable Energy Community, or simply an Energy Community, is a group of actors who organise themselves to produce and share energy from renewable sources locally. The creation of Energy Communities from 2018 onwards is part of Europe's energy transition strategies. The widespread use of renewable energy sources on EU territory is proposed to create a new energy system in which local energy production is strongly encouraged. Energy communities have been developing in European countries for some years, but low-income groups, women and ethnically and culturally marginalised groups tend to be less involved and therefore benefit less. In recent years, however, a different type of energy community has emerged, known as Energy and Solidarity Communities (ESCs). They add social objectives to their primary environmental and economic objectives, namely the inclusion of disadvantaged people in the energy market and, more broadly, the fight against energy poverty, not infrequently in combination with the implementation of local social inclusion programmes.

This section aims to identify the impacts of ESCs in terms of social inclusion and behavioural change at individual and collective levels towards equitable environmental sustainability.

The analysis considers the cases included in RL3 (addressing energy communities, energy poverty and community energy schemes) and PA3 (aimed at encouraging the inclusion of vulnerable groups in energy communities).

4.2. Description of the cases

Overall, 13 cases are considered in this section. A short description of them is given in the table below.

Table 5: The cases considered in PA3 and RL3

Code	Location	Description
EN1	NE	A large building for low-income tenants and immigrants with solar panels providing 75-100% of hot water from April to September.
EN2	NE	A crowdfunded ESC with photovoltaic panels. Most of the associates are students.
EN3	NE	A self-funded ESC, currently in the early stages of development, aimed at supporting local economic activities and residents (particularly women and older people).
EN4	NE	A solar-powered ESC sponsored by the municipality of a big city with low-income, minority, elderly and disabled residents.
EN5	SE	An ESC linked to other social and environmental projects, also involving low-income households and two micro-enterprises.
EN6	SE	An ESC promoted by an organisation supporting people with disabilities and powered by a photovoltaic system donated and maintained by an energy company.

Code	Location	Description
EN7	SE	An ESC for low-income households in a social housing estate, powered by a photovoltaic system financed by a mortgage with a local bank.
EN8	SE	A cooperative in a small rural town involved in community projects to improve energy autonomy, with a particular focus on vulnerable groups and the elderly.
EN9	SE	An energy cooperative of individuals and other cooperatives that provides social services and support to vulnerable households.
EN10	SE	A cooperative focused on sustainability, resilience, renewable energy generation and rural development.
EN11	SE	A cooperative mainly for the elderly, which provides energy through a collective photovoltaic system.
EN12	SE	An ESC located in a low-income area of a big city.
EN13	SE	A consumer cooperative that is in the process of implementing a collective photovoltaic self-consumption system.

4.3. Recorded impact and key challenges

4.3.1. Broadening inclusion

All initiatives prioritise energy poverty and the inclusion of vulnerable people. Several report that, over the past year, they have broadened their engagement with those groups. For example, EN6 is extending its activities beyond the founding institution for disabled people to include nearby disadvantaged households. EN12 is using prize money from PA3 to enable vulnerable families to join the ESC, covering their fees and granting them access to energy and basic self-consumption.

In EN5, organisers aim to reach the most marginalised residents, such as those in informal settlements without legal grid connections, beyond the few disadvantaged families already involved. Likewise, EN4 and EN3 plan to invite additional participants, including low-income families, immigrants and people with disabilities.

This widening of scope has increased the number of vulnerable people benefiting from ESCs and, although precise data is not available, is likely to have had a positive impact on local energy-poverty levels.

4.3.2. Reducing energy costs and boosting efficiency

Another notable impact of these initiatives was a reduction in energy costs for beneficiaries, particularly in ESCs that installed renewable systems (solar or photovoltaic), such as EN1, EN2, EN4, EN6, EN7, EN11 and EN12. This cost saving also translated into improved energy efficiency, driven by two main factors.

The first factor was the implementation of structural measures, for example the installation of insulated windows and doors in EN1, or the renovation of buildings in EN4.

The second factor comprised a series of awareness-raising actions. In EN4, these were designed to promote more sustainable, energy-saving behaviours. In EN5, collective readings of electricity bills helped participants understand how to reduce consumption and costs, thereby encouraging lasting behavioural change. EN2 organised training sessions to enhance knowledge about energy, climate change and sustainable lifestyles.

Together, these structural and educational efforts not only lowered bills but also fostered more efficient energy use among vulnerable households.

4.3.3. Non-energy behavioural changes in ESC initiatives

Several initiatives have also reported non-energy-related behavioural shifts towards environmental sustainability, driven by targeted activities. For example, EN3 organised a permaculture workshop to teach community members and other interested participants how to grow local food and establish community gardens. In EN1, a series of workshops encouraged waste sorting, recycling and better food-preparation techniques. EN5 promoted behaviour change through a dedicated composting project.

However, there is no clear evidence regarding the extent or longevity of these practices. As one promoter of the ESC in EN7 observed, simply joining the ESC does not automatically translate into more sustainable behaviour, but targeted initiatives are needed.

4.3.4. Strengthening social cohesion

Several ESCs have reported notable increases in social cohesion. In EN5, this improvement stemmed from a variety of neighbourhood activities extending well beyond environmental issues, such as award ceremonies and after-school games for children, the creation of a “social concierge” desk offering support and information to vulnerable residents, and neighbourhood parties that included people living in informal settlements.

In EN4, the project leader established a shared green space where disabled and elderly community members could meet, fostering regular interaction, a stronger sense of belonging and mutual support.

These social initiatives often translated into deeper involvement of vulnerable groups in ESC governance. For instance, in EN5, marginalised residents began to play a more influential role; in EN1, low-income migrants increasingly attended decision-making meetings; and in EN4, disabled and elderly participants took on more active responsibilities. In EN3, older low-income residents even assumed leadership positions. Enhanced collective action and coordination, especially between active citizens and local mayors, were also observed in EN8, EN10 and EN11.

Another indicator of strong ESC governance is the high level of trust beneficiaries place in their management. This trust appears to have fostered positive outcomes such as greater self-esteem (noted in EN5 and EN12), pride (in EN1, EN4 and EN6) and optimism (in EN2, EN3 and EN8).

4.3.5. Are ESCs male-dominated?

A notable shortcoming across these initiatives is the absence of measures to tackle gender inequalities. None of the schemes explicitly addressed this issue. Although EN5 and EN7 observed higher levels of activism among women compared to men, leadership roles in both

ESCs remained predominantly male. EN6 stands alone as the only case in which women occupied all leadership positions.

This pattern highlights the need for dedicated gender-equality strategies within ESCs, both to ensure equitable participation and to leverage the full potential of all community members.

4.3.6. The strengths of fragile entities

Energy community schemes (ESCs) are citizen-led groups that can be institutionally and financially vulnerable. However, several factors have bolstered the resilience of some schemes:

- Strong, trustworthy leadership
- Ongoing support and, in some cases, direct involvement by local authorities (e.g., EN1, EN4, EN7, EN9, EN10 and EN11)
- Access to financial backing (for instance, EN6 secured funding through a partnership with an energy company)
- Robust collaboration with actors engaged in social initiatives (e.g., EN3, EN5, EN6, EN8, EN9 and EN10)
- Inclusion in wider networks (for example, EN5 belongs to a regional network of Solidarity ESCs, and EN7 is part of a network promoted by an environmental association)
- High visibility and official recognition (for example, the experience of EN7 is now cited by local authorities as a model for establishing ESCs in small municipalities).

These elements have been critical in transforming otherwise fragile groups into more stable and effective community energy schemes.

4.4. Lessons learned

4.4.1. Leveraging ESCs for sustainability and inclusion

Energy and solidarity communities offer highly effective means of advancing both environmental sustainability and social inclusion. They are uniquely positioned to engage disadvantaged groups in climate action, countering the tendency for such policies to marginalise those with the greatest need. Many ESCs also deliver significant economic benefits, most notably through reduced energy costs.

Despite these advantages and the presence of enabling conditions, the wider adoption of ESCs remains limited. To address this, it is essential to develop and implement support policies at both local and national levels. Such policies should foster an environment that encourages the proliferation, backing and strengthening of ESCs – integrating them not only within environmental policy frameworks but also as a core element of social inclusion strategies.

4.4.2. Harnessing the diversity of models and practices

Despite sharing certain characteristics, each ESC analysed possesses a unique history and distinct features. Some do not even operate their own renewable energy installations, yet they achieve comparable environmental, social and economic benefits. Rather than viewing this diversity as an obstacle, we should regard it as an asset: it makes ESCs highly adaptable,

deeply rooted in their local contexts and flexible enough to address a range of needs and priorities.

To capitalise on this potential, it is crucial to study recent ESC experiences in greater depth, pinpointing the most effective practices and approaches. By doing so, we can inform the establishment of new communities and broaden the impact of existing ones.

4.4.3. Reinforcing the gender perspective

Gender inequality remains largely unaddressed in ESCs, where leadership is dominated by engineers, technicians and local politicians – sectors traditionally occupied by men. By combining social objectives with the environmental and economic aims of energy communities, ESCs could become more gender sensitive. Introducing dedicated gender-equality measures would not only promote fairness but also enhance overall effectiveness, given the central role women play in many aspects of energy use. In strengthening the gender perspective, ESCs can more effectively advance sustainable energy, foster social inclusion and deliver broader economic benefits.

4.4.4. ESCs as catalysts for collective action and inclusive citizenship

The primary impact of ESCs lies in mobilising individuals to protect shared interests and pursue common objectives. In this respect, they act as a powerful stimulus for civic engagement, fostering collective actions that frequently mature into genuine expressions of active citizenship. However, it has been noted that disadvantaged groups are rarely represented in ESC management: a significant shortcoming that must be addressed with deliberate inclusion strategies. Consequently, the current landscape should not be viewed as a final outcome; many ESCs still have further steps to take to ensure truly inclusive governance.

5. Environmental sustainability in micro-businesses led by vulnerable entrepreneurs

5.1. Background

The European Green Deal acknowledges the vital role that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) can and should play in the transition to a more sustainable future. However, many SMEs, particularly micro-businesses led by disadvantaged individuals, are often left out of this process. This exclusion stems largely from a lack of awareness about climate change, coupled with significant barriers such as limited resources, insufficient skills, and a lack of incentives or external support to implement environmentally friendly practices.

Despite these challenges, some micro-entrepreneurs, often operating in vulnerable conditions, are taking steps toward environmental sustainability. These measures include switching to LED lighting, installing solar or photovoltaic panels, sorting waste, using eco-friendly products, reducing transport-related carbon emissions (for example, opting for cargo shipping over air freight), and using sustainable packaging materials like recyclable cardboard.

This section explores these dynamics among a group of disadvantaged micro-entrepreneurs. It aims to shed light on how and under what conditions a shift toward greener practices occurs, the obstacles encountered along the way, and the outcomes of such initiatives.

The section draws upon insights from Research Line 4 (RL4), which examines the adoption of environmental sustainability measures in micro-enterprises, and Pilot Action 4 (PA4), which supports Roma micro-entrepreneurs in Albania in implementing environmentally sustainable practices.

5.2. Description of the cases

The analysis is based on 24 case studies (corresponding to disadvantaged micro-entrepreneurs) located across six countries: Albania (3 cases), Belgium (5), Greece (4), Italy (4), Norway (4), and Romania (4). The Albanian cases were part of PA4, while the remaining cases were included in the second research cycle of RL4.

The table below presents the vulnerability factors affecting these micro-entrepreneurs. It is important to note that individuals may be exposed to more than one factor of vulnerability.

Table 6: Vulnerability factors to which micro-entrepreneurs were exposed

Vulnerability grounds	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	Albania
Gender	5	3	2	-	3	3
LGBTQ+ status	-	1	1	-	-	-
Migrant/Nationality	5	2	3	3	1	-
Social class	1	-	2	-	-	2
Language	-	-	-	3	1	3
Political discrimination	-	-	1	-	-	-
Religion/Ethnicity	2	-	-	-	-	3
Age	-	3	-	1	2	-
Geographic location	-	-	-	1	-	-
Other	1	-	-	-	-	-

The table below presents the economic sectors in which the micro-enterprises operate. It is important to note that some enterprises may be active in more than one sector.

Table 7: Economic sector of the micro enterprises

	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	Albania
Hotels/B&B	1	1	-	-	-	-
Food service (restaurant, bar, pub, bakery)	1	1	3	2	3	-
Culture (e.g., bookshop), environmental products, and Leisure	1	-	1	1	1	1
Waste disposal	-	-	-	-	-	1
Textile/fashion	2	-	1	-	-	1
Handcrafted products (including jewellery)	1	2	-	-	-	-
Retailers (e.g., plastic, electrical installations)	-	-	-	1	1	-

5.3. Recorded impact and key challenges

5.3.1. Micro-businesses can and do engage in sustainability efforts

Nearly all the 24 micro-entrepreneurs surveyed have taken steps to improve the environmental sustainability of their businesses and continue to build on these efforts. Fifteen have made notable investments in this area, with seven doing so to a significant extent and eight to a moderate extent. The majority had already implemented at least some sustainability measures. In 20 out of the 24 cases, environmental action is not a one-time effort but an ongoing or well-established practice.

Some of these enterprises operate directly within the green economy. Examples include two agri-food businesses, one enterprise offering photovoltaic system installations, and an initiative focused on recycling waste from disadvantaged groups.

The actions taken are diverse and cover areas such as improving energy efficiency, switching to renewable energy sources, conducting energy audits, sorting and recycling waste, eliminating plastic in favour of biodegradable materials, promoting sustainable mobility, adopting ethical standards in the food and textile sectors, and running environmental awareness activities, including eco-feminist projects. Nineteen of the 24 businesses combined several of these measures across different fields.

Although no quantitative data on emissions is available, the widespread adoption of these practices suggests a likely reduction in environmental impact. Fifteen micro-enterprises took steps to increase energy efficiency. Six made use of renewable energy, including three that installed photovoltaic systems and three that used electric vehicles for deliveries or purchasing. In addition, three textile micro-enterprises reduced their transport emissions by choosing cargo ships over air freight when importing products from India, Rwanda and Sierra Leone.

5.3.2. Personal behaviour and inclusiveness

Almost all of the micro-entrepreneurs reported changes in their personal behaviours that reflect a stronger commitment to environmental sustainability. These changes most commonly involve recycling and waste sorting, mentioned in 18 cases. The extent of these practices varies depending on national and local regulations. Other frequently mentioned changes include the use of sustainable energy, reported by 12 micro-entrepreneurs, sustainable mobility choices in 13 cases, and more environmentally conscious food consumption in 7 cases.

In addition to personal sustainability efforts, this form of entrepreneurship also supports social inclusion. All 24 micro-enterprises are led by vulnerable entrepreneurs, many with intersectional backgrounds. In 13 cases, they also employ others from their family or community, with most businesses engaging between two and ten people. These enterprises not only promote sustainable practices but also create inclusive employment opportunities.

5.3.3. An empowerment process

An important dimension of the experience shared by the micro-entrepreneurs involves a process of empowerment. All participants reported an increasing ability to identify and address the barriers that influence the adoption of more sustainable practices in their businesses. The most frequently cited challenge was limited financial resources, mentioned in all 24 cases.

Other common barriers included lack of time (18 cases), unfavourable policies or political conditions (14), bureaucratic obstacles (14), broader social and economic constraints (12), and limited access to relevant knowledge (10).

In parallel, most micro-entrepreneurs also improved their capacity to access subsidies, incentives, or other opportunities that support environmental sustainability, with 21 reporting increased awareness or ability in this area. These developments suggest a broader process of learning and empowerment that supports both sustainability and resilience in their professional paths.

5.3.4. Positive outcomes for different disadvantaged groups

People with different vulnerabilities appear to have benefited from the initiatives. The overall impact was particularly positive for migrant micro-entrepreneurs, 14 of whom reported improvements in social status and recognition. Similar positive effects were observed among the three Roma entrepreneurs and in one of the two businesses owned by LGBTQ people.

It is also worth noting that 15 of the 24 micro-entrepreneurs are women, and the majority of people employed in these enterprises are also women.

5.3.5. High confidence in own actions, but frustration with political support

Most micro-entrepreneurs expressed strong confidence in the sustainability of the environmental measures adopted in their businesses. Eighteen reported feeling very confident, while four were somewhat confident. Similarly, 18 out of 24 felt optimistic about the long-term sustainability or growth of their enterprise.

However, levels of satisfaction with the policy and regulatory environment are much lower. Only six out of 21 micro-entrepreneurs described themselves as very satisfied, while 16 reported only moderate satisfaction. Two were not satisfied at all. Among those working alongside them, including family members, employees or partners, five expressed high satisfaction and ten reported a moderate level.

This relatively low satisfaction appears to result from the ongoing and often frustrating barriers faced when adopting environmentally friendly solutions. Entrepreneurs often described how limited resources, lack of time and insufficient support contribute to a sense of frustration and, at times, disorientation. These persistent constraints seem to undercut the strong belief in the value and sustainability of their efforts.

5.3.6. The fragility of the sustainability orientation

Micro-enterprises face significant challenges in adopting and maintaining sustainability-oriented measures over time. These challenges are largely attributable to the inherent weaknesses of micro-enterprises, such as a lack of qualified human resources, limited time, and competing urgent priorities, as well as to a shortage of support, including limited access to incentives and other funding opportunities, and a lack of mentoring. These difficulties are further exacerbated when the business is led by individuals from vulnerable groups. Several other factors contribute to the fragility of the sustainability measures implemented by these businesses.

One key issue is the lack of local support for their environmental initiatives. The micro-enterprises studied rarely received positive feedback for their sustainability efforts. In only four cases did they receive a strong local response. For example, one micro-entrepreneur

renovated a bar and restaurant in a public park, for which he was responsible and became a reference point for environmental action in the neighbourhood. In other instances, customers were dissatisfied with the environmental measures because they resulted in higher prices for the products or services offered.

Another contributing factor is the isolation of micro-enterprises from environmental networks. While 18 micro-entrepreneurs belonged to or had some form of connection to a network, only five were part of an environmental or energy-related network. Most entrepreneurs were involved in solidarity networks (11 cases) or cultural/ethnic networks (9 cases).

The limited recognition of their sustainability efforts at the local level, along with the absence of strong connections to networks focused on environmental sustainability, makes the environmental orientation of these micro-enterprises particularly fragile. This fragility is compounded by the underlying economic vulnerability of many micro-enterprises, further hindering their ability to sustain their green initiatives.

5.4. Lessons learned

5.4.1. Understanding micro-enterprises as drivers of change towards sustainability

SMEs make up 99% of all enterprises in the EU, employing around 100 million people and contributing 56% of the EU's GDP. Most of these are micro-enterprises. Even if only a small share adopts greener practices, the collective impact could be substantial. However, without adequate support, micro-enterprises risk hindering sustainability efforts if they lack the capacity to implement green measures. So far, the European Green Deal and related national plans have not included targeted support for vulnerable micro-enterprises in relation to environmental sustainability. It may be time to shift perspective and recognise these businesses not as barriers, but as potential drivers of sustainable change.

An initial step is to improve understanding of the nature and environmental impact of micro-enterprises led by disadvantaged individuals. At the same time, their capacities should be strengthened, not only through public initiatives such as European projects and national policies, but also via business associations, trade bodies, and support networks, particularly in accessing incentives and opportunities. Strengthening links between micro-enterprises and energy-efficiency networks or similar structures would also support more sustainable practices.

5.4.2. Adopting a multidimensional approach to micro-enterprises

As observed in other sectors, policymakers often act in isolation, leading to the separation of environmental, economic, and social policies. This risk is also present when approaching micro-enterprises. These businesses should not only be seen as economic units but also as vehicles for social inclusion, benefiting both their owners and employees. Additionally, they serve as, albeit fragile, promoters of sustainability measures. To strengthen the Green Deal in a way that is inclusive, effective, and economically viable, a multidimensional and integrated approach to micro-enterprises is necessary. This approach must integrate diverse policy perspectives to fully realise the potential of micro-enterprises in contributing to sustainability goals. A first illustrative step could be to include vulnerable micro-enterprises within the scope of the EU LIFE Clean Energy Transition (CET) 2025 programme: Funding opportunities for the industry sector, where they are currently not specifically addressed.

5.4.3. Preserving diversity

The measures taken by micro-entrepreneurs to enhance the environmental sustainability of their businesses exhibit a high degree of diversity. This diversity arises from various factors, including the personal orientations and experiences of the entrepreneurs and the specific economic sectors in which the businesses operate. It is important to preserve and encourage this diversity, as it enables micro-enterprises to adapt to different internal conditions and external contexts, helping them survive and thrive over time. Sustainability policies should avoid imposing standardised solutions that may only be effective for a limited type of business. Instead, they should offer differentiated mechanisms that cater to the unique needs of diverse micro-enterprises (such as sector-specific incentives, territorial networks, sectoral networks connected to specific value chains, thematic consultancy desks – see also section 5.4.4 below).

5.4.4. Addressing fragility

The fragility of the sustainability orientation of micro-enterprises is a significant issue that needs to be addressed. Their ability to sustain sustainability measures over time is threatened by the inherent weaknesses of micro-enterprises, particularly those run by individuals from vulnerable groups. This fragility is compounded by a lack of positive response and recognition at the local level, as well as isolation from sustainability-related networks, like EENs (Energy Efficiency Networks). Encouraging cooperation between micro-enterprises involved in environmental sustainability could be crucial, as it would help them address common challenges. These challenges might include operating in the same economic sector, being located in the same geographical area, or being part of the same value chain. Local authorities, drawing on their in-depth knowledge of the area's entrepreneurial fabric, could play a highly effective role in fostering greater cooperation between micro-enterprises and larger businesses within the same value chain. Finally, there is a pressing need for more accessible support mechanisms moving beyond one-size-fits-all approaches. These include simplified access to targeted funding, the development of dedicated mentoring schemes, and training programmes tailored to the micro-enterprises' specific capacities and constraints, as in the case of the programme supporting Roma micro-entrepreneurs.

6. Sustainable food

6.1. Background

Food has become a central focus of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the United Nations 2030 Agenda, and European policies. Three key challenges are associated with food. The first is food security, meaning the need to ensure that individuals have reliable access to enough affordable and nutritious food. The second challenge, closely linked to the first, is ensuring that the most vulnerable groups in society have equal access to food, both physically and financially. This includes preventing situations where they are limited to food that is of poorer quality, less nutritious, potentially harmful to their health, or not respecting their religious beliefs or values (e.g., veganism, vegetarianism). The third challenge is to guarantee that food production and consumption are environmentally sustainable and do not cause irreversible environmental damage, whether in the short or long term.

This section considers initiatives that address these issues with the aim of improving access to sustainable food for vulnerable groups. It seeks to assess their impact, identify key challenges, and draw out lessons learned.

This section focuses on PA5 (focusing on an exchange platform between actors involved with community gardens or agrifood systems), PA6 (aimed at producing an action plan and a toolkit for healthy and sustainable food in schools), RL5 (analysing experiences aimed at improving food security and healthy diets in vulnerable communities) and RL6 (exploring the relationship between values associated with Environmentally Sustainable Food Consumption and food-related behavioural change).

6.2. Description of the cases

Overall, 23 cases are considered. A short description is given in the table below.

Table 8: The cases considered in PA5, PA6, RL5 and RL6.

Code	Location	Description
FD1	CEE	Enhancement and promotion of a digital platform to connect community gardens
FD2	WE	A community-based, donation-funded garden, established and managed by an NGO
FD3	WE	A centre providing services for homeless and low-income people, operated by a volunteer organisation
FD4	SE	A social solidarity project operated which also includes a cultivation field for vegetables and fruit
FD5	SE	A programme managed by a non-profit organisation aimed at saving food from many sources and offering it to charities that help people who are facing food insecurity
FD6	SE	A project comprising several urban and community gardens, managed by a municipal company
FD7	SE	An urban garden managed privately by an association engaged with environmental issues
FD8	NE	An organisation that cooks and delivers sustainable food to people in need
FD9	NE	A community-based non-profit organisation providing food, showers, laundry, a place to rest and socialisation opportunities to disadvantaged groups

Code	Location	Description
FD10	CEE	A community garden created under a local neighbourhood gardens project
FD11	CEE	A community garden created under a local neighbourhood gardens project
FD12	SE	A project aimed at developing an action plan and an educational toolkit to promote sustainable food in schools
FD13	WE	A 5-hour initiative centred on cooking activities and shared meals
FD14	WE	A 4-hour initiative on cooking activities and shared meals
FD15	WE	An initiative aimed at delivering local food
FD16	WE	A 5-hour community kitchen initiative
FD17	WE	A 1-day free food booth
FD18	SE	A 4-hour social kitchen and cooking literacy workshop
FD19	SE	A 4-hour edible forest walk, including a documentary projection
FD20	CEE	A 4-day small-scale producers' food fair
FD21	CEE	A 4-hour cooking literacy workshop using local and ecologically produced vegetables
FD22	CEE	A 2-day online set of vegan seminars
FD23	CEE	A 1-day vegan summit including panels and speeches and vegan product testing

Although roughly, the following types of initiatives can be identified:

- 7 gardening-focused initiatives
- 6 initiatives focused on food-related services provision
- 2 food exhibitions
- 3 focused on cooking activities and shared meals
- 5 food-related cultural/awareness-raising initiatives.

6.3. Recorded impact and key challenges

6.3.1. A strong potential for change

The initiatives studied demonstrate a strong potential to bring about immediate changes in awareness, values and perceptions related to sustainable food. This type of impact is observed in nearly all the initiatives, regardless of their specific nature or target groups. For

example, those involving community gardens increased awareness of the importance of sustainable agricultural practices. Several other initiatives promoted greater understanding of ecological food values and behaviours. In particular, FD12 contributed to raising awareness among key stakeholders, including school administrators, policy makers, teachers and parents, about the sustainability of food systems and practices, as well as the principles of the Farm to Fork Strategy.

In general, longer-term interventions developed on the basis of infrastructure, such as community gardens, tend to have broader, more continuous and deeper impacts. However, they require more time and investment, and are more exposed to risks, including the generation of tensions and conflicts. Interventions that are narrower in scope, quicker to implement and shorter in duration are less problematic and can reach a wider audience, but they tend to have more limited, discontinuous and superficial impacts. Impact is less apparent in initiatives aimed at providing direct food assistance to the most disadvantaged, such as those involving food delivery to people in need or to individuals experiencing homelessness.

6.3.2. Community bonds grow around shared food activities

The initiatives analysed tend to support the creation of new social connections, often contributing to greater social inclusion. This impact is closely linked to the central role that food can play in fostering a sense of togetherness and, in some cases, in enabling forms of community building. In certain initiatives, this was a planned outcome, while in others it emerged as an unplanned but positive result of food-related activities.

This effect has been particularly evident in community gardening projects, where social cooperation increased around the management of the garden, food production, the sharing or distribution of produce, and the exchange of cultivation techniques. Similar outcomes were also noted in some of the shorter initiatives studied under RL6, where vulnerable individuals, such as elderly people, reported an increased sense of inclusion.

However, the process of building social links is not always without challenges. Some initiatives encountered tensions between individuals or between different ethnic groups, highlighting the complexity of community dynamics in diverse settings.

6.3.3. Vulnerable groups often active but rarely leading

All the initiatives studied place a strong focus on vulnerable groups, but the roles these groups play can vary significantly. In community gardening projects, vulnerable individuals often take on active roles and, in some cases, even leadership responsibilities. In contrast, within initiatives aimed at supporting the most disadvantaged, such as those under RL5, their capacity for proactive engagement is often limited by the immediate challenges they face.

In initiatives specifically designed to change food-related behaviours, vulnerable groups usually participate actively. However, the short duration of many of these projects means that their longer-term impact remains uncertain. In the case of FD12, vulnerable groups were involved through participatory workshops that helped shape an educational toolkit, although they did not have a central role in leading the initiative.

Overall, the available data suggest that vulnerable groups often contribute proactively. Yet aside from a few cases linked to community gardens, they rarely hold a leading position within the initiatives. To enable this shift, participatory mechanisms, long-term initiatives, capacity building, and recognition of local knowledge are essential. However, these alone may not be

sufficient to empower the most vulnerable individuals as leaders or co-creators, as their circumstances often compel them to prioritise more immediate needs. To address this, partnerships that emphasise collaboration, resource sharing, and inclusive engagement, as well as flexible funding mechanisms, should be tested to provide tailored support suited to specific contexts and barriers. Where appropriate, flexible funding can facilitate the distribution of financial or other resources directly to vulnerable individuals, helping to overcome the economic constraints that often hinder their participation.

6.3.4. Strong gender engagement but limited intersectional insight

The initiatives studied show a strong gender perspective, particularly through the prominent role played by women. This likely reflects the continued centrality of women in food-related responsibilities, including production, preparation and management. Many initiatives actively encouraged women's participation and leadership, often through targeted actions. Women's involvement is particularly evident in initiatives aimed at changing food-related practices, such as those under RL6, and in the school-focused initiative FD12. In several community garden projects, women also played leading roles. For example, in FD22, women were responsible for planting and crop production, and in other cases in Southern and Western Europe, they were prominently represented on the boards managing community gardens.

6.3.5. Effective use of local knowledge to drive behavioural change

Food-related initiatives stand out for their strong integration of local and traditional knowledge, which is often directly linked to changes in behaviour. In some cases, knowledge exchange and brokerage were planned from the outset, while in others they developed more organically. For instance, several initiatives within RLs 5 and 6 included activities that promoted the sharing of sustainable food preparation techniques and traditional recipes, with the aim of encouraging shifts in food-related behaviours. Community garden projects, such as FD10 and FD11, featured exchanges on traditional cultivation methods and cooking practices, including those from migrants' countries of origin. These exchanges not only supported changes in dietary habits but also helped strengthen community ties.

6.3.6. Valuable but institutionally fragile initiatives

Although the initiatives analysed show a clear capacity to generate impact, many of them appear to be institutionally fragile. This fragility is not unique to those working on sustainable food and social inclusion, but it is particularly relevant in this context. The sustainability of these initiatives is undermined by a combination of challenges. These include limited financial resources, insufficient support from public authorities and private sponsors, as well as organisational, bureaucratic and logistical constraints. In some cases, an unsupportive legal framework further exacerbates their vulnerability. The report on the RL6 initiatives specifically underlined this issue, noting that while similar actions are relatively widespread, they often face the persistent risk of interruption or collapse. This jeopardises their ability to ensure continuity and long-term impact.

6.4. Lessons learned

6.4.1. Leveraging food initiatives to bridge sustainability and inclusion

The analysis of the initiatives suggests that food is a particularly effective entry point for addressing the intersection of environmental sustainability and social inclusion. It is relevant

to everyone and plays a critical role in the daily lives of many vulnerable groups. Food systems have a major environmental impact, whether positive or negative, and there is a wealth of knowledge that can be applied and shared in this domain. Supporting food initiatives through longer-term, simplified grants and municipal partnerships can be key to advancing both environmental and social goals.

6.4.2. Supporting fragile initiatives through local collaboration

The analysis highlights the range of intervention methods and strategies that can be used to reinforce the connection between nutrition and social inclusion. This diversity should be maintained and encouraged. However, many initiatives, especially those with a bottom-up approach, are institutionally, financially and organisationally fragile. They often operate in isolation, with limited resources and uncertain futures, and they tend to lack visibility. A collaborative environment should therefore be encouraged. Promoting broader cooperation among initiative leaders, including relevant stakeholders, is necessary. Strengthening connections among them, especially at the local level, could help amplify the impact of their work and ensure greater continuity.

6.4.3. Encouraging cross-sector partnerships

The initiatives analysed have made a notable difference in attitudes and behaviours and, in many cases, have influenced the social conditions of vulnerable groups. However, the approaches often remain narrowly focused, sometimes due to limited resources or a specific mission, such as addressing only cooking, food waste, production or school-based food initiatives. To increase their impact, it would be beneficial to adopt broader and more integrated approaches. This could involve fostering cooperation between organisations addressing different vulnerabilities, such as food and housing, food and energy or food and employment. It could also mean communicating a broader perspective on the benefits of food initiatives. For instance, community gardening projects can be valued not only for their role in food production but also for the ecosystem services they provide, such as urban cooling and biodiversity enhancement. Encouraging such integrated strategies may be facilitated by joint funding schemes that support projects delivering both social and environmental outcomes

7. Sustainable mobility

7.1. Background

Mobility is a crucial component of the Green Deal, with the EU's 2030 climate change targets aiming to reduce congestion and pollution from transport. Achieving these goals requires promoting collective transport and increasing mobility options based on walking and cycling. This involves investing in mobility infrastructure, implementing restrictions on car use, and introducing new policies, standards, and regulations. However, shifting towards more sustainable forms of mobility also necessitates significant changes in individuals' personal behaviours and lifestyles, as well as profound cultural shifts within society.

At the same time, policies intended to promote this modal shift could have unintended negative consequences for disadvantaged groups, particularly those living in socially and physically marginalised neighbourhoods. These policies might inadvertently deepen social inequalities.

This section explores these dynamics, focusing on initiatives promoted or studied by the ACCTING project that examine the relationship between sustainable mobility and social inclusion, with particular emphasis on cycling inclusion.

The section is based on the cases included in PA7 (supporting student cycling commutes to school in disadvantaged neighbourhoods) PA8 (aiming at connecting cycling and social justice initiatives) and RL7 (focusing on transport poverty and sustainable travel through cycling in socially vulnerable areas).

7.2. Description of the cases

Overall, 14 cases are considered. They are briefly presented in the table below

Table 9: The cases considered in PA7, PA8, and RL7

Code	Location	Description
MO1	CEE	An initiative aimed at promoting cycling and cycling education among youngsters in a disadvantaged area of a city
MO2	WE	A cycling school initiative that teaches participants how to ride a bike and improves their cycling skills
MO3	WE	A bike-to-school initiative that also includes actions to favour a shift toward more sustainable modes of transport at the local level
MO4	SE	A team that organises events aimed at promoting and the principle of sustainable mobility
MO5	SE	A spontaneous movement of children, parents and volunteers that brings children to school by bike on the last Friday of the month in many schools in a big city
MO6	SE	A bike kitchen located in a building occupied by families from different migrant backgrounds and with precarious socio-economic situations
MO7	SE	An initiative to promote the use of bicycles in disadvantaged neighbourhoods
MO8	SE	An initiative to promote inclusion in cycling by making bicycles accessible to groups that might otherwise have limited access
MO9	CEE	An initiative focusing on the installation of bike racks and the promotion of cycling in two high schools
MO10	CEE	An initiative encouraging participants to use the bicycle as a means of transport
MO11	NE	An initiative for training and try-out cycling for senior citizens
MO12	NE	An initiative for training and try-out cycling for people with disabilities

Code	Location	Description
MO13	NE	A cycling school operating in different disadvantaged neighbourhoods
MO14	SE	A project combining activities to promote the use of bicycles for vulnerable groups, advocacy actions and the creation of a space for dialogue and coordination for grassroots organisations

7.3. Recorded impact and key challenges

7.3.1. Promising impact on cycling behaviour for vulnerable groups

The impact of cycling initiatives has been notably positive, demonstrating strong effectiveness in influencing mobility behaviours. For instance, interviews with participants from 11 initiatives analysed in RL7 revealed that 74% expressed an intention to cycle more as a result of the initiative. The data also highlighted a significant impact on the lives of disadvantaged individuals. Many vulnerable participants learned to cycle, gained confidence cycling in urban traffic, or were able to cycle more regularly due to the initiatives.

Cycling initiatives also appear particularly effective in engaging disadvantaged groups, such as low-income families and immigrants, for whom cycling can serve as a vital mode of transport. Additionally, for the elderly and people with disabilities, cycling offers an opportunity for increased autonomy and greater integration.

7.3.2. The link between cycling initiatives and system-level policies

Cycling initiatives, more than those in other areas, require policy support at the system level to reach their full potential. This includes structural support like cycling planning and infrastructure (e.g., bike lanes), as well as regulatory measures (e.g., traffic laws and incentives). However, local authorities often fail to provide the necessary support. Despite this, some cycling initiatives have successfully bridged this gap by establishing connections with local authorities. For instance, MO14 worked on coordinating civil society organisations to foster cooperation with local governments, while MO4 promoters acted as consultants for cycling mobility in their city. In MO3, promoters collected traffic data to influence local transport policies. Similar collaborations were found in Northern European initiatives (MO11, MO12, and MO13).

7.3.3. Cycling initiatives as drivers of social empowerment

A notable aspect of cycling initiatives is their positive impact on vulnerable individuals, particularly in terms of autonomy and independence. For example, the promoters of MO1 reported that families were pleased with the increased independence their children gained through cycling. Similarly, promoters of bike kitchen initiatives, such as MO6 and MO7, have highlighted how learning bicycle maintenance and repair skills fosters a sense of self-sufficiency and boosts independence. For many vulnerable groups, such as migrant women, the ability to travel independently in an environmentally sustainable way is an empowering factor that can open up additional opportunities. This sense of autonomy and increased self-esteem can facilitate access to broader social and economic opportunities. Gaining knowledge of the wider territory is also an important achievement, involving an understanding of the city

beyond one's neighbourhood, and the ability to access places, public services, and potential employers, rather than being confined to one's immediate area of residence.

Overall, cycling promotion initiatives appear particularly effective in aligning environmental and social objectives, achieving both with minimal conflict and tension.

7.3.4. Car culture as a barrier to cycling inclusion

A recurring theme in interviews with beneficiaries of cycling initiatives is the absence of dedicated bike lanes and the feeling of vulnerability when sharing the road with cars. Many report aggressive behaviour from motorists, which contributes to making cycling an unpleasant or even intimidating experience. This may lead participants to reduce or give up cycling altogether.

The idea that bicycles and public transport could replace cars as primary modes of urban mobility remains a distant prospect for many citizens and local policymakers. In some cases, political dynamics reinforce this challenge. For instance, the promoters of MO14 reported that a change in local government resulted in a more hostile attitude toward cycling, creating a less favourable policy environment and slowing momentum for sustainable mobility reforms.

7.3.5. Volunteering as a critical issue

A particularly critical issue in the cycling domain is the difficulty in recruiting and retaining volunteers. This challenge is often intensified by the demanding nature of many cycling-related activities, which typically require volunteers to have specific technical skills. Because of limited funding, many initiatives cannot afford to hire staff, relying almost entirely on volunteer efforts.

This constraint often limits the ability of even the most effective initiatives to grow or expand their reach. For example, the promoters of MO8 successfully ran a bike school that had a positive impact on a small group of participants in a single neighbourhood. Yet despite the success, the lack of volunteers and funding prevented the project from scaling up. Similar problems have affected bike-to-school initiatives, which require a relatively large number of adult volunteers – albeit for short periods – to safely accompany children on their commutes.

7.3.6. Structural barriers limiting the role of vulnerable groups

Cycling initiatives in the ACTING project paid close attention to the diverse forms of vulnerability, including age, disability, economic background, cultural or social marginalisation, and migrant status. Many adopted targeted strategies to meet these varying needs. Notable examples include the tricycle bike schools in MO11 and MO12, aimed at elderly and disabled participants, and the women-only cycling groups promoted in MO14, which addressed both cultural and safety-related barriers to female cycling.

Despite this targeted outreach, the involvement of vulnerable groups remains largely limited to their role as beneficiaries. Even in participatory initiatives, disadvantaged individuals rarely assume leadership roles or take part in coordination or planning activities. This limited agency may be partly explained by the structural constraints many face, such as the inability to volunteer due to financial pressure or the unaffordability of bicycles. While some initiatives (e.g., MO1) attempted to address this by providing bicycles to participants, these measures only partially mitigate the underlying problem of exclusion through economic self-selection.

7.4. Lessons learned

7.4.1. Designing cycling initiatives to optimise their change potential

Cycling initiatives have shown strong potential to promote sustainable mobility while fostering the empowerment of vulnerable individuals. Their value extends far beyond teaching people to ride a bike. When well designed, these initiatives can enhance independence, expand inclusion opportunities, build self-esteem, and nurture a sense of community, while simultaneously contributing to environmental goals. However, to fully realise their transformative potential, these initiatives must be carefully planned to address a wide range of barriers. These include the cost of acquiring a bicycle, the hostility of some citizens and politicians towards cyclists, the lack of supportive infrastructure, and safety concerns. Furthermore, initiatives must be flexible and responsive to the diverse needs of their target groups and adaptable to varied policy environments.

7.4.2. Creating connections between cycling initiatives and system policies

The cases analysed highlight the need for long-term institutional anchoring of community cycling initiatives within urban and transport planning frameworks. Creating synergies and cooperation between multi-level local authorities, regulatory bodies, and community-led efforts can significantly enhance the effectiveness and reach of cycling-related interventions.

Greater coordination could align infrastructure development and regulatory frameworks with the goals of social inclusion and sustainable mobility. Facilitating more consistent interaction between civic actors and decision-makers can help ensure that community needs are integrated into urban mobility strategies and that promising initiatives receive the structural backing they need to scale and endure. The appointment of bicycle mayors, i.e. civic figures supported by local authorities, can play a key role in fostering engagement and, as seen in the case of MO1, in promoting pilot initiatives that pave the way for more structural investments, such as the development of bike lanes.

7.4.3. Diversifying cycling initiatives to support a new mobility culture

Differentiation is a strong point of cycling promotion initiatives. They differ in their general approach (cycle schools, cycle to school, cycle kitchens) and in the wide range of activities they carry out (women-only cycle rides, installation of cycle lanes, tours, mass cycle rides, not to mention workshops for low-cost maintenance of bicycles, training activities, lessons in schools, purchase and provision of low-cost bicycles, creation of networks and coordination bodies to influence decision-making processes, or promotion of tricycles for disabled or elderly people), potentially reaching many types of vulnerable groups. Cycling initiatives offer multiple routes to sustainable mobility.

To maximise their effectiveness, it's crucial to map and involve a broad spectrum of civil society actors. Engaging these stakeholders in participatory planning processes allows for the integration of varied social perspectives, practices, and innovative ideas, thereby enriching the portfolio of inclusive cycling initiatives responding to a diverse set of needs.

7.4.4. Beyond cycling: building cross-sector support

Despite their demonstrated potential, cycling initiatives often face persistent barriers that limit their expansion and long-term sustainability. These include financial uncertainty, limited institutional support, and difficulty attracting and retaining skilled volunteers. Such constraints

can prevent even the most impactful initiatives from growing or becoming embedded in the wider mobility landscape.

To overcome these challenges, it is essential to explore new strategies aimed at enhancing sustainability and scalability. This includes forming broader partnerships, beyond the cycling domain, with other grassroots, social, or community-based actors. Some of the initiatives analysed have already begun experimenting in this direction, forging alliances and testing hybrid funding models or involving private and third-sector actors. These emerging approaches offer promising avenues for reinforcing the stability and reach of cycling initiatives. Establishing structured channels for dialogue, co-design workshops, and shared planning tools can also foster more stable and constructive cooperation between cycling initiatives and municipalities, particularly when, as in the case of MO14, civil society actors form a coordination structure to advance shared proposals.

7.4.5. Overcoming cultural barriers to active mobility

Cycling initiatives often face deep-rooted cultural resistance linked to the dominance of car-centric thinking. This resistance manifests itself not only in policy and infrastructure priorities, but also in social norms and everyday perceptions.

Certain social groups have a stigma attached to cycling: in some communities, women cyclists are frowned upon; older or disabled people may avoid using tricycles out of embarrassment or fear of being seen as weak; and cyclists in general are often seen as a nuisance. There is also a persistent belief that cycling infrastructure is unnecessary or even dangerous, e.g., reducing customer access to shops, or that cycling is irrelevant to serious urban mobility challenges.

These perceptions are fuelled by a car culture that continues to see cycling as marginal or impractical. To reduce stigma and challenge car-centric mindsets, cultural change must be central to cycling strategies. This involves bringing cycling classes into schools, sharing relatable stories, using inclusive language, and highlighting cycling as practical, safe, sustainable and joyful. Public campaigns should connect cycling to shared values like health, freedom, and clean air. Collaborating with local voices and showcasing visible change in public spaces can help shift perceptions.

8. Volunteering

8.1. Background

An expansion of volunteering and voluntary action is essential to support a socially just environmental transition. As shown in other sections of this report, such an expansion cannot be taken for granted. Numerous factors constrain the action of volunteers and voluntary organisations working at the intersection of environmental issues and social inclusion. These include a lack of institutional recognition, difficulties in accessing both public and private funding, overt hostility from certain political parties, burdensome and slow bureaucratic procedures, and the absence of supportive policy frameworks.

This section examines the impact of the initiatives carried out under the ACCTING project aimed at increasing voluntary activity and engagement in the fields of environmental sustainability and social inclusion. The analysis draws on two specific actions: PA9 (a national

platform to connect volunteers with local initiatives), and PA10 (a programme offering secondary school students structured opportunities to engage in volunteering).

8.2. Description of the cases

PA9 aimed to create a digital platform in a Central and Eastern European (CEE) country to serve as a space for connecting volunteers with projects and local initiatives led by informal groups, NGOs, civil society organisations (CSOs), private companies and individual citizens. The purpose was to increase the visibility of volunteering activities and to make it easier for members of the community to get involved.

PA10 focused on engaging a group of students aged 14 to 17 from a secondary school located in a neighbourhood marked by significant economic and social disadvantage, in a large city in Southern Europe. The initiative aimed to familiarise the students with the concept of environmental transition and to involve them in volunteering activities organised by local NGOs and CSOs.

The two initiatives differ in geographical scale, with PA9 operating at a national level and PA10 at a local level, and in their strategic approach. PA9 emphasised cooperation and networking through a digital tool, while PA10 concentrated on experiential learning for a specific group of young people. Despite these differences, both shared the same overarching objective of supporting volunteering and promoting a culture of civic engagement focused on environmental and social inclusion.

8.3. Recorded impact and key challenges

8.3.1. Boosting the potential of informal volunteering

PA9 and PA10 both target young people who may wish to dedicate part of their time to social and environmental initiatives, rather than focusing on staff within voluntary organisations. They address what might be described as informal or 'granular' volunteering, which is more closely tied to grassroots involvement and individuals' personal lives than to professionalised or institutional volunteering.

This segment of volunteering is often overlooked or undervalued, despite its potential to significantly contribute to the promotion of sustainable and inclusive behaviours across the broader population. Recognising and supporting this form of engagement is therefore critical for expanding the reach and cultural relevance of voluntary action.

8.3.2. Volunteering by and for disadvantaged people

The two pilot actions are both aimed at involving disadvantaged individuals as active volunteers. This approach is particularly significant, as disadvantaged people, who often face greater barriers to participating in environmental and social activism due to their exposure to multiple risks, are frequently overlooked in volunteer mobilisation efforts.

This choice deserves attention not only because it is relatively uncommon, but more importantly because it places the empowerment of vulnerable groups through active participation at the centre of these initiatives. In doing so, the pilot actions challenge

conventional models of volunteering that tend to position disadvantaged people solely as recipients of support rather than as agents of change.

8.3.3. Building local ecosystems of engagement

Both initiatives place strong emphasis on fostering connections. PA9 was specifically designed to build new relationships between volunteers, project promoters and potential funders. The pilot action also encouraged the formation of local groups by launching calls for initiatives that required at least five people already connected to one another, and it supported the involvement of local NGOs to strengthen grassroots engagement.

In PA10, secondary school students were trained and took part in volunteering experiences organised by seven different organisations. This gave the students direct exposure to real-world social and environmental activism and helped to foster a local ecosystem of engagement. Facilitating these types of connections appears to be crucial in enabling people to participate in volunteering, even when their commitment is limited or intermittent, and in helping them integrate volunteering into their everyday lives.

Moreover, the development of such linkages is essential to ensure the sustainability of initiatives that aim to promote volunteering as a long-term and systemic practice.

8.3.4. Building community through informal volunteering

In both initiatives, a secondary but significant effect of the pilot actions is the strengthening and densification of community relationships and an enhanced sense of belonging to a place or community. This is a recurring theme, as seen in earlier sections of the report. In this case, the phenomenon is particularly notable because the pilot actions influence even the most basic social ties.

For instance, PA9 requires that funding applications come not from individuals but from informal groups of at least five people. As a result, these groups are often composed of friends, peers who share the same environment, or in some cases, schoolmates or entire classes. This informal composition fosters deeper social cohesion, and the commitment of these groups often endures over time, especially as many apply for funding repeatedly.

In the case of PA10, the sense of community arises from the shared identity of the students, who attend the same school, live in the same neighbourhood, and engage in activities that directly affect their local environment. This proximity to the context enhances both the relevance and the emotional connection participants feel towards the volunteering experience.

8.4. Lessons learned

8.4.1. Tapping informal volunteering for broader engagement

Informal volunteering (including volunteer groups that are not legally registered and that form only occasionally, often based on pre-existing relationships, such as a school class or a group of friends) is a domain of civic engagement that could play a growing role in advancing environmental and social inclusion initiatives. Because it is small-scale and rooted in local social networks, informal volunteering has the potential to involve vulnerable groups directly and provide them with opportunities for empowerment. Its informal and adaptable structure makes it particularly suitable for societies marked by fragmentation and weak social cohesion,

helping to rebuild relationships of cooperation and solidarity, especially in disadvantaged areas.

Furthermore, informal volunteering could serve as a valuable entry point for new volunteers, particularly in the current context where, as highlighted in other sections of this report, it is becoming increasingly difficult to attract and retain people in voluntary roles. As such, promoting this kind of engagement may be an effective strategy for strengthening community ties and achieving broader social goals.

8.4.2. Communicating volunteering as a powerful tool of personal development

Volunteering is a powerful means of promoting personal development for people of all ages, but especially for young people. For this reason, it should be considered an integral part of both educational and socialisation processes. At the same time, voluntary experiences can help individuals acquire specific and transferable skills that may also be valuable in their future professional lives. Volunteering promotes a cultural shift towards the idea that civic engagement can be embedded into one's daily routines and way of life, without necessarily becoming a professional or semi-professional endeavour.

Educational institutions such as schools and universities have an important role to play in supporting this cultural shift. They are well-placed to help normalise volunteering as a meaningful and accessible activity for young people. PA10 points to a number of tools that could encourage schools to become more engaged in this area. These include the development of educational programmes focused on youth activism for a more sustainable society, and the incorporation of internships with voluntary organisations into school-to-work transition schemes.

8.4.3. Strengthening digital infrastructure as a driver for informal volunteering

Digital tools have a key role to play in supporting informal volunteering. The platform developed in PA9 provides a clear example of how digital infrastructure can facilitate this type of engagement. When well designed, digital tools can significantly reduce the barriers for individuals to access relevant information, including opportunities for funding, training resources, and projects promoted by voluntary organisations or informal groups. They can also support interaction and coordination among volunteers.

8.4.4. Raising the visibility of informal volunteering

One of the most significant challenges in promoting widespread and small-scale forms of volunteering is their limited visibility. This is largely due to the dominance of more formal and structured types of volunteering, which tend to receive greater attention and recognition. Even within the formal sector, there is intense competition for visibility among different organisations and fields of action, particularly when it comes to securing public and private funding.

In this competitive landscape, granular and community-based forms of volunteering often remain under the radar. However, rather than being positioned in opposition to established forms of volunteering, these decentralised approaches should be recognised as complementary and capable of working in coordination with more formal structures. Enhancing the visibility of these grassroots efforts is essential to unlock their full potential and ensure they are valued as an integral part of a broader volunteering ecosystem.

9. A cross-cutting analysis of the initiatives

9.1. A comparative view of the impacts

Following the analysis of impacts across the various thematic sectors, we now synthetically evaluate which types of impacts were more or less easily and significantly achieved by each group of initiatives in the different sectors, using the impact evaluation framework presented in Table 2.

To do this, we drew on the summary tables of impact by thematic area presented in the Annex, which are the result of the process described in Section 1.2. For illustrative purposes only, impact areas were assigned a synthetic value for each thematic sector, reflecting the qualitative assessments provided in the relevant tables. The values used were high, medium-high, medium-low, or low. They are indicated with a different colour in the table below.

All assignments were made qualitatively based on the available documentation and the researchers' knowledge of the individual cases and were reviewed iteratively by the research team. In instances where the outcomes of different initiatives within a thematic area were highly divergent, medium-low values were generally assigned, as no clear or consistent trends in impact could be identified.

The outcomes of this evaluation are summarised in the table below.

Table 10: Synthetic view of the impacts identified in all intervention sectors.

Sector	DM	NB	EN	ME	FD	MO	VL
Direct impact areas							
1. Individual or collective pro-environmental behavioural change	Low	Medium-low	High	High	High	High	High
2. Reduction of territorial vulnerabilities and improved sustainability	Medium-low	High	High	High	Medium-low	High	Medium-low
3. Reduction of gender+/intersectional inequalities	Low	Medium-low	Medium-low	Medium-low	High	High	High
Indirect impact areas (precursors of impact)							
4. Agreement and satisfaction of the involved stakeholders	Low	Medium-low	High	Low	Medium-low	High	High
5. Acknowledgement of vulnerable groups as key actors in environmental transitions	Low	Medium-low	Low	High	Medium-low	Low	High
6. Inclusion of local/traditional knowledge	Medium-low	Medium-low	Low	Low	High	Low	Low
Cross-cutting impact areas							
7. Sustainability	Medium-low	High	Medium-low	Medium-low	Low	Low	Medium-low
8. Replicability and scalability	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low

DM = Disaster risk management; NB = Care for nature, biodiversity and land use; EN = Energy and solidarity communities; ME = Disadvantaged micro-entrepreneurs; FD = Sustainable food; MO = Sustainable mobility; VL = Volunteering

H = High impact	MH = Mid-high impact	ML = Mid-low Impact	L = Low impact
------------------------	-----------------------------	----------------------------	-----------------------

While these values are intended only to indicate areas of denser impact, and should thus be viewed as merely illustrative, certain observations can nonetheless be made across the different impact categories: direct impact, indirect impact (precursors of change), and cross-cutting impact.

9.2. Direct impact: evidence of appreciable change

Direct impacts of the analysed initiatives were observed and recorded across a wide range of Research Lines and Pilot Actions. Depending on the specific initiative, the intended change targeted either individual pro-environmental behaviour, particularly among disadvantaged or marginalised groups, or collective entities, especially various types of authorities. Overall, individual behavioural change appears to have been achieved more readily than institutional change. This is particularly evident in the first thematic sector, disaster management, which addressed institutional change within authorities and recorded the lowest impact.

Changes leading to a reduction in territorial vulnerabilities were also frequently reported, particularly in initiatives focused on environmental restoration, energy communities, sustainable entrepreneurship, and mobility. In contrast, achieving change related to the reduction of gender+ inequalities proved more challenging. While some initiatives adopted a gender perspective, implementing intersectional approaches was notably more difficult. Intersectional change tended to emerge more readily in areas such as sustainable food and mobility, as well as through volunteering initiatives. Conversely, such change was reported less consistently in contexts where authorities played a more central role.

Although the analysed initiatives often led to appreciable change during the evaluation period, the limitations and short duration of the available observations prevent us from drawing conclusions about the depth and longer-term sustainability of these changes. Nevertheless, some insights in this regard can be inferred from what we term ‘precursors of change’, i.e., fundamental mechanisms hypothesised to facilitate enduring impact (see next section).

9.3. Indirect impact: mixed evidence of precursors to longer-term change

What we refer to as ‘indirect impacts’ are factors that, according to the ACCTING theory of change, do not constitute impacts in themselves but instead increase the likelihood of achieving deeper and more lasting change.

While participant satisfaction is undeniably important for fostering long-term impact, and was in this case generally quite high, we wish to highlight two more substantive dimensions.

The first concerns the initiatives’ capacity to recognise vulnerable and disadvantaged groups as key agents in driving environmental transitions. The potential of initiatives like those we observed to empower such groups to engage with environmental issues is crucial. People in these groups are often compelled to disregard or reject environmental concerns due to more

immediate challenges, limited resources, or even the risk that the transition itself may threaten their livelihoods.

The second aspect highlights the importance of incorporating local and traditional knowledge into solutions for environmental sustainability. This approach further emphasises the need to include diverse voices and expertise, validating the experiences of different groups and increasing their ownership of the change process.

Addressing these aspects is not easy and requires a demanding process of mutual recognition and negotiation. However, it strengthens the change process by helping to make environmental behaviour an integral part of the identity of those involved, rather than something imposed from outside.

Documented impacts are lower and uneven in these two areas. While the recognition of vulnerable groups as key actors central in at least some of the areas and cases analysed, engaging with the knowledge and expertise of these groups remains particularly challenging. Disaster management and nature restoration initiatives show more potential in this regard, but it is in the domain of sustainable food where that knowledge has proven most effective in building communities and grounding change within the communities themselves.

More in general, it can be said that working on what we consider to be precursors of deeper and longer-lasting change still requires considerable effort to be effectively operationalised and more consistently integrated into bottom-up environmental initiatives.

9.4. Cross-cutting impact: the challenge of sustainability and replicability/scalability

Sustainability was often considered from an early stage of implementation, and some initiatives demonstrated moderate to strong potential to continue beyond the funding period. However, replicability and scalability appear significantly weaker, often constrained by limited human resources and insufficient institutional and political support. This underscores the fragility of bottom-up initiatives and raises further concerns about their actual potential to drive lasting change.

Results have been mixed, leading to low overall scores. Some initiatives were designed to integrate from the outset into existing partnerships with public bodies, creating a supportive environment for scaling up. Others struggled to establish structured relationships or align with institutional priorities. These outcomes are heavily influenced by the thematic area and contextual factors, including the political climate and its evolution.

It should be noted, however, that this is also the area where the limitations of our analysis are most apparent, as the timeframe is clearly too short to allow for a reliable assessment of these dimensions.

10. Conclusions

This section presents an additional set of cross-cutting conclusions, drawing out key lessons learned from the full range of initiatives analysed. These insights are organised into four overarching themes that consistently emerged, with selected examples from the thematic sections above referenced for illustration:

- The **cultural shifts** that initiatives must foster to support an inclusive and sustainable transition
- The importance of activating individual and collective **agency for change**, while constructively engaging with resistance
- The **strategies for action** that increase the likelihood of achieving deep, long-lasting change
- The **resources and relations** that must be mobilised to address the inherent fragility of many initiatives

10.1. Cultural shifts: beyond environmental awareness

Promoting inclusive behavioural change and sustainable practices, both at the individual and institutional levels, requires a wide range of cultural shifts. The cases analysed show that these shifts must extend beyond purely environmental values and culture. A consistent finding is that deeply rooted cultural attitudes and practices need to be challenged across multiple related domains in order to enable meaningful change.

Selected examples from the observed initiatives

- Improving disaster preparedness and management through more inclusive and locally responsive practices demands a shift in how civil protection institutions perceive control. These institutions often view volunteers and local knowledge holders, especially those unaffiliated with formal NGOs, as sources of disruption or unreliability. To make progress, it is essential to foster a culture that values local expertise and contributions, alongside developing appropriate tools for collaboration and the joint design of preparedness and response strategies (thematic area DM/Disaster risk management).
- Cycling can carry a stigma for different cultural reasons: it may be associated with low socio-economic status, seen as inappropriate for women in certain cultures, or viewed unfavourably by car drivers in contexts where car culture is dominant. Older or disabled people may avoid using adapted bicycles for fear of being perceived as weak. Moreover, cultural change is needed not only in public attitudes but also in policymaking, where cycling infrastructure is still too often deprioritised as irrelevant or even detrimental to traffic flow and local commerce (thematic area MO/Sustainable mobility).

10.2. Agency: the social dimension of change and resistance

Individual agency for pro-environmental behavioural change was more likely to emerge in settings where community-based approaches were adopted, particularly in the presence of

strong social support and peer influence dynamics. Several cases also demonstrated the activation of collective agency in support of pro-environmental attitudes. In some instances, collective agency took the form of resistance. However, if approached in a genuinely inclusive manner, resistance can become a catalyst for meaningful change.

The focus on the social dimension of change is especially pertinent when considering disadvantaged groups, who may encounter additional barriers to initiating substantial change processes in their lives.

Selected examples from the observed initiatives

- Fostering community building has played a crucial role in many sustainable and healthy food initiatives, where individual agency for dietary change has been activated through the formation of new social ties and increased social inclusion. In community gardening projects, social cooperation emerged around garden management, food production, the sharing and distribution of produce, and the exchange of cultivation techniques and recipes (thematic area FD/Sustainable food).
- Marginalised groups played an active role in environmental protection activities across a broad range of sectors, including flood prevention and opposition to coal mining. In some cases, however, they also resisted reforestation projects or decarbonisation measures that posed a threat to their livelihoods. Initiating a process of dialogue and negotiation around their concerns helped to strengthen their role as agents of change and prevented them from being forced into anti-environmental positions (thematic area NB/Care for nature, biodiversity and land use).

10.3. Strategic action: engaging with social-environmental tensions

The initiatives analysed focused on sustainability transitions in different sectors, each involving tensions around the trade-off between social and environmental needs and priorities, each time shaped by specific natural and socio-economic contexts. The most impactful initiatives have successfully engaged with these tensions, developing practices that not only navigate them but even harness them as drivers of progress by identifying social-environmental synergies. Within this broader strategy, diversification also emerged as a key factor for success, supporting adaptation and alignment with the local combination of environmental and social objectives and challenges.

Selected examples from the observed initiatives

- Many initiatives that focused on environmental conservation also pursued social objectives, such as the integration of marginalised groups and social cohesion. In some cases, this approach allowed social and environmental aims to reinforce each other, for example through the creation of employment opportunities. A similar outcome was often made possible through collaboration with public sector actors (thematic area NB/Care for nature, biodiversity and land use).
- Other initiatives, like Energy and Solidarity Communities (ESCs), proved particularly well placed to bridge environmental and social priorities. These initiatives involve disadvantaged groups in climate action, helping to counter the tendency of such policies to marginalise those with the greatest needs, while also delivering significant economic

benefits, particularly through reduced energy costs. In terms of diversification, although energy and solidarity communities often share common traits, each one is shaped by its own background and specific characteristics. In some cases, ESCs do not even manage their own renewable energy systems, yet they still deliver similar outcomes in terms of environmental, social, and economic impact. This variation allows ESCs to remain highly responsive to local conditions, making them well-suited to address diverse challenges and priorities (thematic area EN/Energy and solidarity communities).

- Diverse types of cycling initiatives also offer multiple routes to inclusive, sustainable travel, effectively aligning environmental and social objectives. A notable feature of these initiatives is their positive impact on vulnerable individuals, especially in terms of autonomy and independence. For many in these groups, the ability to travel independently in an environmentally sustainable way is empowering and facilitates access to wider social and economic opportunities (thematic area MO/Sustainable mobility).

10.4. Resources and relations: pooling and coordinating efforts

While the initiatives analysed demonstrate a strong potential for impact, many remain institutionally fragile. Their sustainability is threatened by limited funding, inconsistent support from public and private actors, and various bureaucratic and logistical challenges. In some cases, an unsupportive legal framework adds to their vulnerability, leaving them at risk of disruption and undermining their continuity and long-term impact. Although grassroots initiatives cannot alter system-level conditions on their own, building alliances and partnerships has emerged as a viable strategy to improve access to resources and favour engagement with decision-makers.

Cross-sectoral alliances and partnerships can also serve the dual purpose of pooling resources and providing more holistic support to disadvantaged groups through coordinated action across areas such as food, housing, energy, employment, and mobility.

Selected examples from the observed initiatives

- For vulnerable micro-enterprises, an association has been found between participation in various types of networks and engagement with sustainability practices. These networks can connect enterprises based on factors such as locality, sector, or country of origin, (for migrant micro-entrepreneurs). Alternatively, networks may be established with larger businesses within the value chain, offering access to greater resources, including knowledge and expertise on environmental issues and measures (thematic area ME/Disadvantaged micro-entrepreneurs).
- In the cycling sector, an initiative sought to connect cycling activism with social justice, creating a platform for dialogue and collaboration among organisations and grassroots groups through inclusive engagement methods. This led to a joint programme of activities. In addition to improving the optimisation of organisational resources and reaching a broader range of disadvantaged groups, coordination has facilitated greater access to institutional decision-making spaces (thematic area MO/Sustainable mobility).
- A different initiative focused on developing a digital platform to link volunteers with various projects and local initiatives organised by informal groups, NGOs, civil society organisations, private enterprises, and individuals. Its primary aim was to enhance the visibility of volunteer activities and simplify the process for community members to

engage. The initiative prioritised collaboration and networking, offering support to both individual volunteers and organisations, including smaller ones, while fostering a culture of civic participation centred on social and environmental inclusion (thematic area VL/Volunteering).

11. Limitations

The numerous limitations of the report arise from its very ambition to capture the impacts of multiple initiatives of varying types, implemented in diverse contexts and domains. The most significant of these are outlined below.

Comparability of the initiatives. The degree of homogeneity among initiatives within the same thematic sectors varied. For instance, solidarity and energy communities were relatively similar, while initiatives focused on disaster management or sustainable food showed considerable diversity. Differences across thematic sectors were even more pronounced. Although the use of a shared impact evaluation framework helped introduce some coherence, comparability was only achievable at a higher level of abstraction. This limited the ability to identify detailed impact patterns and to draw specific lessons learned.

Different approach to impact assessment in RLs and PAs. Comparability is also limited by the different approaches to impact assessment used to analyse RLs and PAs (research in the case of RLs and monitoring and evaluation for the PAs), and the consequent difference in the amount and detail of information available for the different cases.

Self-reporting bias. This further constrains the generalisability of the results. In the case of the PAs, in particular, though not exclusively, a degree of self-reporting bias can be identified, making it difficult to fully assess the reliability of the reported impacts.

Time constraints. The experimental activities were subject to significant time limitations. The Pilot Actions (PAs) typically lasted for only around one year, and although some of the initiatives within the Research Lines (RLs) spanned a longer period, they too could only be observed for a relatively short time. This represents one of the most significant limitations for impact assessment. To mitigate this, we introduced the category of *impact precursors*; however, this approach does not fully overcome the limitation.

References

Balkmar, D., Sandström, L., Pugliese, F., Cacace, M., Aglietti, C., Fonseca, M. L., Esteves, A., Ferreira, D., Kerremans, A., Vogelzang, M., Denis, D., Stergiadis, C., Chatzibirros, V., Vivas, A. B., Popușoi, S., & Holman, A., (2025). *ACCTING Report on Research Line 7: Cycling Initiatives for an Inclusive Mobility Transition*. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1552559

Boostani, P., Vilhelmsen, K., Pellegrini Masini, G., Quinti, G., Pugliese, F., & Cacace, M. (2025). *ACCTING Report on Research Line 3: Leveraging Behavioural Change for Inclusive Energy Communities*. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1552588

Botha, D. & Niethammer, J. (2025). Pilot Action Implementation Report. ACCTING Deliverable D5.7. Submitted to the European Commission 31.03.2025. [10.5281/zenodo.15275658](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15275658).

Boyer, B., Cook, J., & Steinberg, M. (2011). *Recipes for Systemic Change: The Helsinki Design Lab Studio Model*. Sitra. Available at:

https://www.helsinkidesignlab.org/peoplepods/themes/hdl/downloads/In_Studio-Recipes_for_Systemic_Change.pdf

Cousins, J. B., & Whitmore, E. (1998). Framing participatory evaluation. *New directions for evaluation*, 1998(80), 5-23. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ev.1114>

Denis, A. & Strid, S. (2024). Open studios: Using better stories and personas to develop inclusive solutions to reduce inequalities. In: *Sage Research Methods: Diversifying and Decolonizing Research*. SAGE Publications. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781529691481>

Fetterman, D. M., & Wandersman, A. (2007). Empowerment evaluation: Yesterday, today, and tomorrow. *American Journal of Evaluation*, 28(2), 179–198. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1098214007301350>

Gajdusek, MF., Szüdi, G., Altınay, AG., Düzel, E., Fonseca, ML., Ferreira, D., Prundeanu, O. (2025). *ACCTING Report on Research Line 2: Exploring Behavioural Change at Places Affected by Biodiversity Change from the Perspective of Vulnerable Groups*. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15525904

Moreno, L., Fonseca, M. L., Abrantes, P., Borhan Türeli, B., Zorell, C., Stergiadis, C., Gajdusek, M. F., Altınay, A. G., Düzel, E., Chatzimpyros, V., & Bolibok, O., & Miliadi, V. (2025). *ACCTING Report on Research Line 5: Inclusive Food Security and Sustainable Healthy Eating*. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15525801

Patton, M. Q. (1994). Developmental evaluation. *Evaluation practice*, 15(3), 311-319. <https://doi.org/10.1177/109821409401500312>

Patton, M. Q. (2006). Evaluation for the way we work. *Nonprofit Quarterly*, 13(1), 28-33. Available at: <https://nonprofitquarterly.org/evaluation-for-the-way-we-work/>

Pugliese, F., Cacace, M., Marta, F., Aglietti, C., d'Andrea, L., Fonseca, M.L., Esteves, A., Ferreira, D., Pellegrini Masini, G., Löfström, E., Vilhelmsen, K., Gehlmann, F., Balkmar, D.,

Sandström, L., Stergiadis, C., Chatzibirros, V., Holman, A., & Popușoi, S. (2025). *ACCTING Report on Research Line 8: Toward a Just Mobility Transition: Responses of Vulnerable Groups to Car-Restrictive Policies*. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15520004

Quinti, G., Pugliese, F., Denis, A., Kerremans, A., Pellegrini Masini, G., Vilhelmsen, K., Chatzibirros, V., Stergiadis, C., Holman, A., & Popusoi, S. (2025). *ACCTING Report on Research Line 4: Environmental Sustainability and Vulnerability: Cases of Micro-Enterprises led by Disadvantaged Entrepreneurs*. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15525858

Strid, S., & Denis, A. (2024). Using design-thinking approaches to diversify and co-create solutions to wicked problems with multiple stakeholders. In: *Sage Research Methods: Diversifying and Decolonizing Research*. SAGE Publications.

<https://doi.org/10.4135/9781529691528>

White, J., Altınay, A.G., Conceição, C., Düzel, E., Fragoso, M., Pugliese, F., Quinti, G., Sandström, L., Borhan Türeli, B., Vasconcelos, J., & Zorell, C. (2025). *ACCTING Report on Research Line 1: Valorising Local Knowledge on Natural Hazards*. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15525938

ANNEX: Synthetic view of the recorded impacts

The following tables summarise the main impacts identified in the analysis, according to the evaluation framework presented in the first part of the report.

Thematic area: Local knowledge and inclusiveness in disaster risk management

Synthetic view of the impacts identified in RL1 and PA1

No.	Impact area	Comments
1	Individual or collective pro-environmental behavioural change	<p>Some level of collective (institutional) change was documented in all the cases, but the number of people significantly involved within each institution remained limited.</p> <p>In a rather uneven way, institutional change was reported in three areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changes in the governance of disaster prevention, preparedness and response through the adoption of a community-based approach in decision-making and daily working practices. - Changes in the way authorities engage with local/traditional knowledge, improving responsiveness to local issues. - Strengthened community-based preparedness and recovery management. <p>At the individual level, increased environmental awareness and pro-environmental behaviour are observed, often constrained by limited participation.</p>
2	Reduction of territorial vulnerabilities and improved sustainability	<p>A general improvement in DRM capacities was reported in terms of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved local institutional capacity for climate change adaptation - Increased resilience to exogenous shocks (including planning) - Improved protection of environmental resources (in a few cases). <p>A higher awareness among authorities of the complexity of social vulnerability and its impact on DRM was also noted.</p>
3	Reduction of gender+/intersectional inequalities	<p>Some positive trends were observed in reducing gender+ inequalities in participation in disaster prevention, preparedness, and response governance. However, these advances were often met with resistance or neglect and occurred within a broader context of (often) limited overall citizen participation in disaster risk management (DRM) governance.</p>
4	Agreement and satisfaction of participants	<p>The orientations of the participants are quite diverse, even within individual cases, which makes it difficult to give a uniform assessment. Low levels of satisfaction seem to prevail.</p>
5	Acknowledgement of vulnerable groups as key actors in environmental	<p>Participation of vulnerable and disadvantaged groups in the design of prevention measures and management of crisis situations is rare; cases of empowerment of women/vulnerable groups are more common. Very few structural changes in DRM governance have</p>

No.	Impact area	Comments
	transitions	been observed in terms of increased participation of the most vulnerable.
6	Inclusion of local/traditional knowledge	The introduction or strengthening of knowledge pluralisation practices in disaster prevention, preparedness and response has been observed in rural areas. In urban and peri-urban areas, local knowledge was generally considered less relevant and more likely to be overlooked by authorities.
7	Sustainability	Community-based tools, once adopted, tend to be maintained over time as they become part of the procedures adopted by the authorities.
8	Replicability and scalability	Most of the practices were considered too context-specific to be replicated. There were a few exceptions. Some good practices were considered to be scalable, but only with a great deal of adaptation.
9	Unexpected or additional impacts	Some unexpected impacts were recorded, albeit rarely: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policies to regularise and professionalise community engagement may also discourage local practices and agency. - The formalisation of roles within authoritative structures may lead to the ossification of engagement practices and new divisions between the authorities and the communities. - When staged in a top-down way, disaster education and awareness raising may preclude opportunities for more self-directed community learning and realisation.

Thematic area: Care for nature, biodiversity, and land use

Synthetic view of the impacts identified in PA2 and RL2

No.	Impact area	Comments
1	Individual or collective pro-environmental behavioural change	The initiatives generally led to an increase in citizens' environmental awareness. However, shifts towards more environmentally friendly personal behaviour were more limited. At the institutional level, the attitude of the relevant authorities appeared more open to forms of negotiation and dialogue with citizens.
2	Reduction of territorial vulnerabilities and improved sustainability	Most initiatives entailed some change in the use (or exploitation) of resources in the area, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stoppage or slowdown of anti-ecological interventions - Changes in land use, water use, biodiversity and natural balance, reforestation. In addition, increased social cohesion/group solidarity was recorded and, in a few cases, the creation of employment opportunities.

No.	Impact area	Comments
		Finally, a widespread increase in active citizenship (building networks, proactive communities, community alliances, and changing spheres of activism) must be highlighted.
3	Reduction of gender+/intersectional inequalities	A general focus on the role of women was observed in most cases. An intersectional approach was usually lacking.
4	Agreement and satisfaction of participants	All citizens agreed to take part in the initiatives. Their satisfaction level is generally reported as high, but it is not always well documented.
5	Acknowledgement of vulnerable groups as key actors in environmental transitions	Most actions empowered women or disadvantaged actors such as migrants, pastoralist/transhumant communities or elders. Some initiatives were led (or self-organised) by vulnerable groups or at least involved their active participation.
6	Inclusion of local/traditional knowledge	In several cases, local and traditional knowledge (e.g., of elders or women) has been valorised (e.g., in river basin management and restoration, or in documenting local biodiversity along pastoral routes).
7	Sustainability	In many cases, the promoters of the initiatives expressed their commitment to continuing the initiatives that have been undertaken or are underway, building on, among other things, a shared vision of a liveable future, improved leadership, networking and alliances.
8	Replicability and scalability	Although some experiences can be used as good practices that can be scaled up or replicated in areas with similar ecosystems and cultural contexts, this possibility was rarely considered by the promoters of the initiatives.
9	Unexpected or additional impacts	No unexpected or additional impact was reported.

Thematic area: Energy and solidarity communities

Synthetic view of the impacts identified in PA3 and RL3.

No.		Impact area	Comments
1		Individual or collective pro-environmental behavioural change	<p>The initiatives certainly led to an increased focus of the Energy Communities on energy poverty, also linked to an increased capacity of the ECs' promoters and leaders to include vulnerable people.</p> <p>There is also evidence of increased environmental awareness among those involved in the ESCs.</p> <p>Behavioural changes in personal lifestyles related to energy consumption were also reported in some cases. Environmental behaviours not related to energy consumption (e.g., waste recycling) were reported as rare.</p>
2		Reduction of territorial vulnerabilities and improved sustainability	Many of the analysed ESCs have contributed to reducing the energy consumption and costs of ESC members (thus reducing energy poverty) and to switching to renewable energy.
3		Reduction of gender+/-intersectional inequalities	While a relevant number of vulnerable people have benefited from the analysed ESCs, no impact on gender inequality is reported, which seems to be a recurring weakness of ECs.
4		Agreement and satisfaction of participants	Quite strong agreement and satisfaction of participants (leaders and ESC associates) with the change processes generated by the ESCs and their effects are generally reported, often based on a high level of trust in the ESC and its leadership.
5		Acknowledgment of vulnerable groups as key actors in environmental transitions	Although much attention has been paid to promoting the participation of members of vulnerable groups in ESCs, this has rarely translated into their access to leadership positions.
6		Inclusion of local/traditional knowledge	Except for a few related, non-energy initiatives, such as community-led food preparation, there are no documented mechanisms for integrating participants' knowledge into the management or development of the ESCs.

No.		Impact area	Comments
7		Sustainability	Sustainability issues are oftentimes considered by ESCs. They tend to have some factors that facilitate their sustainability, such as the existence of an energy infrastructure, the availability of economic resources, cooperation between different social actors, strong leadership and support from local authorities. However, ESCs remain relatively fragile in institutional and financial terms.
8		Replicability and scalability	The replicability and scalability of these schemes are seldom addressed. However, some examples have been identified: participation of the ESC in a wider network of energy communities; increased visibility, which eases access to support from local, national and European institutions; and the ability to present ESCs themselves as a transferable model.
9		Unexpected or additional impacts	Scarcely documented; notable examples include the promotion of the region's image in one case and the mitigation of rural decline in another.

Thematic area: Environmental sustainability in micro-businesses led by vulnerable entrepreneurs

Synthetic view of the impacts identified in PA4 and RL4.

No.	Impact area	Comments
1	Individual or collective pro-environmental behavioural change	Behavioural changes among micro-entrepreneurs are documented, resulting in improved environmental awareness, adoption of more environmentally sound behaviours and overall improved environmental sustainability of micro-enterprises run by vulnerable entrepreneurs.
2	Reduction of territorial vulnerabilities and improved sustainability	Most of the micro-entrepreneurs made improvements, albeit often modest, to the environmental footprint of their businesses. These improvements primarily involved increasing the share of renewable energy used and/or enhancing the energy efficiency of their micro-enterprises and related ecosystems.
3	Reduction of gender+/intersectional inequalities	Many women leading micro-businesses have been identified, although no specific impact on gender equality has been recorded.

No.	Impact area	Comments
4	Agreement and satisfaction of participants	Most micro-entrepreneurs expressed confidence in the environmental measures they had implemented in their businesses. However, some reported dissatisfaction, expressing a desire to do more but feeling hindered by numerous barriers and a lack of adequate support.
5	Acknowledgement of vulnerable groups as key actors in environmental transitions	All micro-entrepreneurs were vulnerable to varying degrees, and all are now engaged in managing environmental transitions. In a few cases have they begun to play a proactive or leadership role in the larger business ecosystem.
6	Inclusion of local/traditional knowledge	The consideration of local or traditional knowledge was very rare. It happens only for some among the Roma micro-entrepreneurs
7	Sustainability	Overall, micro-entrepreneurs are confident that the sustainability measures they have adopted will endure over time, and many intend to maintain their focus on environmental practices. However, they also highlight the challenges they have faced, citing factors such as isolation and limited local support. While participation in networks focused on energy efficiency and environmental issues can be beneficial, such engagement remains relatively rare.
8	Replicability and scalability	The replicability and scalability of these initiatives largely depend on shifting from individual efforts to collective action, particularly through the participation of micro-entrepreneurs in existing or newly formed networks. However, as noted above, such participation occurred only in a few cases during the project period.
9	Unexpected or additional impacts	No unexpected impacts were mentioned.

Thematic area: Sustainable food

Synthetic view of the impacts identified in PA5, PA6, RL5 and RL6.

No.	Impact area	Comments
1	Individual or collective pro-environmental behavioural change	<p><i>Three main types of behavioural change are documented as being quite widespread in the initiatives:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changes in awareness and perception of sustainable food - Changes in food-related practices - Creation of new social links fostering social inclusion (especially in the case of community gardening-centred initiatives).
2	Reduction of territorial	The initiatives addressed different vulnerability factors (e.g., low-

No.	Impact area	Comments
	vulnerabilities and improved sustainability	income, social isolation, access to healthy food). In some cases, due to the nature of the initiatives, these factors could only be addressed in a superficial and indirect way. In other cases (particularly those focused on community gardens), the approach tended to be deeper and broader.
3	Reduction of gender+/intersectional inequalities	Women's participation was strongly supported, also because of the disproportionate role they still play in food-related issues. The role of women in leadership positions is documented in some initiatives. Changes in gender roles in food-related practices are reported in some cases. The use of an intersectional lens in the approach is rarely mentioned.
4	Agreement and satisfaction of participants	Participants' agreement and satisfaction are not systematically reported but tended on average to be quite high.
5	Acknowledgement of vulnerable groups as key actors in environmental transitions	The focus on vulnerable groups as targets is strong in all cases. Vulnerable participants rarely play a leading role in RL6 initiatives, while they are more involved in RL5, which in some cases also succeeds in including extremely vulnerable groups.
6	Inclusion of local/traditional knowledge	Inclusive knowledge practices are promoted or emerge spontaneously in many cases.
7	Sustainability	The sustainability of the smaller initiatives is in general weak, while larger ones have in some cases secured funds and public support.
8	Replicability and scalability	Replicability and scalability are reported to have been usually poorly considered by the promoters of the initiatives. Replicability is more in focus in the case of the community gardens platform and the introduction of sustainable food in schools.
9	Unexpected or additional impacts	Very few unexpected/additional impacts are reported. Some of them are problematic (e.g., tensions among different vulnerable/marginalised groups), but the majority are positive (e.g., social cohesion emerged as an unintended benefit).

Thematic area: Sustainable mobility

Synthetic view of the impacts identified in PA7, PA8, and RL7.

No.	Impact area	Comments
1	Individual or collective pro-environmental behavioural change	Cycling initiatives are quite effective in activating pro-environmental behavioural changes and raising awareness on sustainable mobility.
2	Reduction of territorial vulnerabilities and improved sustainability	Cycling initiatives were quite sensitive to different types of vulnerability, in some cases developing actions tailored to specific vulnerable groups (for example, low-income families were supported to access a bicycle).
3	Reduction of gender+/intersectional inequalities	Gender issues are often carefully considered in cycling initiatives, as women may face additional barriers to cycling compared to men. These barriers can stem from cultural factors, such as norms within certain immigrant communities or rural areas, as well as concerns around safety. Many initiatives also specifically target older adults, migrants, and people with disabilities, recognising the unique challenges these groups face when it comes to accessing sustainable mobility options like cycling.
4	Agreement and satisfaction of participants	Satisfaction with cycling initiatives was generally high or very high.
5	Acknowledgment of vulnerable groups as key actors in environmental transitions	Vulnerable groups did not play a major role as key actors in the cycling initiatives (with one single exception where this aspect was carefully considered).
6	Inclusion of local/traditional knowledge	Very few two-way knowledge exchanges were reported. Bike-focused initiatives mainly aimed at transferring technical knowledge to beneficiaries, sometimes favouring mutual learning among the latter.
7	Sustainability	The sustainability of cycling initiatives was generally quite limited. There was also a strong self-motivation on the part of the promoters to get involved. Only in a few cases viable solutions were identified during the project lifetime.
8	Replicability and scalability	Many initiatives appeared to be potentially scalable and replicable. However, only in a few cases were conditions found to make this prospect concrete.
9	Unexpected or additional impacts	No relevant unexpected impacts are reported.

Thematic area: Volunteering

Synthetic view of the impacts identified in PA9 and PA10.

No.	Impact area	Comments
1	Individual or collective pro-environmental behavioural change	Changes in awareness and perception of volunteering were reported. Both initiatives managed to create connections involving young people, voluntary entities and, in one of the two cases, funding organisations.
2	Reduction of territorial vulnerabilities and improved sustainability	In both cases, the focus was not on a sector but on promoting volunteering in general. Therefore, different types of vulnerability were considered, depending on the project supported or on the volunteering experience of the students in their training process.
3	Reduction of gender+/intersectional inequalities	Both initiatives kept a gender perspective. One case actively promoted projects with a gender and LGBTQ+ perspective.
4	Agreement and satisfaction of the involved stakeholders	Participants report high levels of agreement and satisfaction.
5	Acknowledgement of vulnerable groups as key actors in environmental transitions	The focus on vulnerable groups as a target group was strong (e.g., young people exposed to different types of vulnerability; pupils at risk of dropping out of school, pupils with specific learning difficulties). In both cases, attention was paid to enabling members of vulnerable groups to become volunteers.
6	Inclusion of local/traditional knowledge	This aspect was not considered in the two PAs, if not sporadically.
7	Sustainability	In both cases, the promoters were committed to taking the initiative forward. In one case, the promoters have developed a plan to ensure their commitment to maintain the platform for three years. In the other case, a number of arrangements have been put in place to enable the initiative to continue.
8	Replicability and scalability	Some initial attempts were made to promote the replicability and scalability of the initiatives (e.g., some informal meetings with other bodies, some public presentation of the initiatives), but it is too early to assess their impact.
9	Unexpected or additional impacts	Few unexpected impacts were reported, mainly showing the interest of participants to continue and deepen their volunteering experience over time.